

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science

IMPLEMENTATION Phase

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D4.3 Revised E-RIHS Business Plan

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ABSTRACT

This document outlines the first version of the *Business Plan 2025-2027 (v1)* for the *European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS)*, developed as part of the European project *Implementation Phase* of E-RIHS (E-RIHS IP) under task *T4.1 Revising E-RIHS Business Plan and Developing a Marketing Strategy*. It supports the transition of E-RIHS into its operational phase, accompanying its forthcoming establishment as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC).

The *E-RIHS ERIC Business Plan 2025-2027 (v1)* details E-RIHS's objectives and strategic priorities, the services provided through its access platforms (ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB) and HS Academy training programs, the governance and organizational structure, the human resources strategy, the marketing positioning, and the financial framework necessary to support its operation. It also addresses the expected impacts and outlines the steps for the implementation, including quality assessment and risk management, providing a comprehensive structured plan to guide E-RIHS through this critical stage of its lifecycle development.

The document reflects contributions from all project Work Packages and incorporates insights from key project deliverables to ensure alignment with the E-RIHS's evolving strategic and operational context in Europe and beyond.

The *E-RIHS ERIC Business Plan 2025-2027 (v1)* is intended as a baseline document that will be further refined with the inputs of the ERIC's governance bodies after their formal establishment.

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INTRODUCTION

The deliverable *D4.3 Revised E-RIHS Business Plan* presents the first version of the *E-RIHS ERIC Business Plan 2025-2027 (v1)*, a key document supporting the transition of the *European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS)* into its initial operational phase as it prepares for establishment as a *European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)*. It outlines strategic priorities, access and training service provisions, governance and organizational structure, human resources strategy, marketing positioning, financial framework and steps for the implementation, including quality assessment and risk management, necessary to guide E-RIHS through this critical stage of its lifecycle.

This document has been developed within the framework of task *T4.1 Revising E-RIHS Business Plan and Developing a Marketing Strategy of E-RIHS IP*. It reflects the collaborative contributions of all Work Package leaders and integrates insights from various strategic and operational documents produced during the project.

The development of this business plan was also informed by the analysis presented in *D4.1 E-RIHS Business Plan: Approach to its Revisions*,¹ which provided the strategic framework for this update. Building on the foundation of the *D11.1 E-RIHS Business Plan v1.01 (2020)*,² this revised version incorporates significant changes in operational, strategic, and policy documents.

In preparing this update, key reference documents were considered, including the *E-RIHS Statutes (v10.04.3)*,³ *Annex II Financial (v0.5.3)*,⁴ *E-RIHS ERIC Scientific and Technical Description (v 5.02)*,⁵ *Costbook (ver. 0.7)*,⁶ and the *E-RIHS Scientific Strategy (v1.0)*.⁷ The financial figures have been revised to align with the current configuration of participating countries in the ERIC, ensuring an accurate representation of operational needs and contributions.

This *E-RIHS ERIC Business Plan 2025-2027 (v1)* is intended as a baseline document that will be further refined once E-RIHS ERIC is established, with the inputs of its formally constituted governance bodies.

¹ Nardello, I., Strlič, M., & Virgili, V. (2023). *E-RIHS IP D4.1 E-RIHS Business Plan: Approach to its revision*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10184948>.

² Pezzati, L., Castillejo, M., Mimoso, J., Padfield, J., Striova, J., & Strlič, M. (2020). *E-RIHS PP D11.1 Business Plan (1.01)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10224313>.

³ E-RIHS. (2024). *E-RIHS Statutes (v10.04.3)*. European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

⁴ E-RIHS. (2024). *Annex II Financial (v0.5.3)*. European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

⁵ E-RIHS. (2022). *E-RIHS Scientific and Technical Description (STD) (v5.02)*. European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

⁶ E-RIHS. (2020). *E-RIHS Costbook (v0.7)*. European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

⁷ Bertrand, L., Anglos, D., De Clercq, H., Castillejo, M., Spring, M., Charbonnel, B., David, S., & Dubray, F. (2020). *E-RIHS PP D9.3 E-RIHS Scientific Strategy (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4045832>.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Europe is home to an extraordinary wealth of cultural heritage, including unique works of art, collections, heritage sites, monuments, archaeology, cultural landscapes and other expressions of material culture. This rich heritage intertwines diverse cultures across Europe, forming the foundation of cohesive societies, thriving economic sectors like cultural and creative industries and tourism, and nurturing the sense of belonging.

E-RIHS, the *European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science*, is an interdisciplinary, distributed infrastructure aimed at advancing research and delivering cutting-edge solutions that enhance the understanding, preservation and appreciation of cultural heritage. E-RIHS ERIC, established under EU law, ensures its effective operation across Europe and globally.

Vision and Mission. E-RIHS aspires to ensure that heritage remains accessible and meaningful across generations, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration to enhance its understanding, conservation, and appreciation. Its mission is to lead heritage science advancement globally by providing cutting-edge facilities, resources and data, driving innovation, and empowering communities to address critical challenges while ensuring heritage continues to benefit society and drive sustainable growth.

Services. E-RIHS ERIC gathers this expertise and provides the know-how, research capacity and access through four main platforms: ARCHLAB - gathering archives of scientific information and reference collections, FIXLAB - a wide range of stationary analytical facilities, MOLAB - the mobile laboratory units of the infrastructure, and DIGILAB - digital knowledge and data repositories used across the sector, along with collaborative tools development and related virtual research environments. Beyond the availability of a formidable range of outstanding instruments, datasets and expertise related to heritage and its historical context, E-RIHS ERIC generates and disseminates new research activities, engages audiences, enables and organizes training through its HS Academy, supports organizations and managers in the development of standards and policies, and makes available a range of specialized services and products.

Governance and Organization. E-RIHS ERIC's governance structure is designed to ensure efficient and transparent operations. The Central Hub, based in Florence, Italy, coordinates activities and serves as the primary access point for users. National Nodes represent the infrastructure at the national level, ensuring cohesive integration across member countries, i.e., Italy (host country), Cyprus, France, Hungary, Malta, the Netherlands, Slovenia, Spain, Poland, Romania, and the United Kingdom, as well as ICCROM as perspective permanent observer. The governance bodies include the General Assembly, the Director General assisted by the Central Hub, the Committee of National Nodes and the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board.

Management and Human Resources. E-RIHS ERIC's success depends on a well-structured management system and highly skilled human resources. The Central Hub oversees daily operations, ensuring coordination among National Nodes and partners. Human resources policies focus on fostering interdisciplinary expertise, professional development, and collaboration across disciplines to maintain a dynamic and effective workforce.

Financial and Funding Framework. E-RIHS ERIC operates on a sustainable financial model that combines in-cash and in-kind contributions from member countries. The annual contributions support the infrastructure's operational needs, including access services, training programs, and outreach activities. The financial framework also includes provisions for adapting to the evolving needs of the infrastructure and its stakeholders.

Quality Assurance and Risk Management. Quality is a cornerstone of E-RIHS's operations. The infrastructure employs rigorous quality assurance procedures, including performance indicators and regular assessments, to maintain high standards across all services and activities. A comprehensive risk management strategy ensures resilience and sustainability, identifying potential risks and developing effective mitigation measures.

Market Positioning and Outreach. E-RIHS ERIC positions itself as a leader in heritage science. Outreach strategies aim to engage stakeholders, promote awareness, and attract new users by emphasizing the infrastructure's value in addressing global heritage science challenges.

Impact. E-RIHS ERIC generates significant impacts across scientific, societal, and economic domains. It drives innovation and expands knowledge in heritage science through interdisciplinary research. It reinforces the societal value of cultural heritage as a resource for education, social cohesion, and public engagement. Economically, it supports industries such as cultural and creative sectors, and tourism, fostering sustainable growth and creating new opportunities.

The E-RIHS's long-term strategy focuses on expanding its global reach, integrating new technologies, and fostering collaborations that address emerging challenges in heritage science.

1. E-RIHS OBJECTIVES AND STRATEGY

E-RIHS, the *European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science*, is an interdisciplinary, distributed infrastructure aimed at advancing research and delivering cutting-edge solutions that enhance the understanding, preservation and appreciation of cultural heritage.

E-RIHS ERIC is the *European Research Infrastructure Consortium*, the legal entity established under EU law to manage and ensure the effective operation of the research infrastructure at both pan-European and global levels.

1.1 VISION AND MISSION

1.1.1 Vision

The E-RIHS vision is to ensure that heritage remains accessible, relevant and meaningful in a diverse and changing world, for the benefit of present and future generations. By fostering collaboration across disciplines and borders, and blending innovative technologies with cultural insights, E-RIHS investigates material heritage with the aim of its optimal preservation and to reveal the rich artistic and historical narratives they embody. By advancing knowledge, conservation, and impactful use of heritage in society, E-RIHS generates environmental, social, and economic growth, ensuring it remains a vital shared resource for humanity that drives sustainable development and enriches the lives of citizens.⁸

1.1.2 Mission

The mission of E-RIHS is to advance heritage science as a global leader by providing researchers and professionals with integrated access to a unique array of cutting-edge laboratories, mobile instruments, archives, collections, expertise, open data and research resources. By driving scientific breakthroughs and offering highly specialized training, E-RIHS empowers communities to address critical research challenges in understanding, sustainable preservation, responsible management and appreciation of cultural heritage. E-RIHS stimulates innovation in heritage practices, supports interdisciplinary collaboration, promotes best practices, and develops standards, protocols and interoperability of tools and data. Through the empowerment of communities of practice across both public and private sectors, and through impactful initiatives in advocacy, public engagement and outreach, E-RIHS ensures that cultural heritage continues to inspire, connect and benefit the society for generations to come.⁹

⁸ The vision articulated herein builds on and updates the vision outlined in the *E-RIHS Scientific and Technical Description (v5.02) (2022)*, aligning heritage science research with contemporary challenges and opportunities.

⁹ The mission articulated herein has been elaborated and refined, building on the mission outlined in the *E-RIHS Scientific and Technical Description (v5.02) (2022)*, to achieve greater focus and alignment with the evolving needs of heritage science research.

1.2 ADDED VALUE CAPABILITIES AND STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES

E-RIHS is a model of interdisciplinary and hybrid research infrastructure that integrates SSH and STEM as well as physical and digital access platforms. It fulfils its mission by implementing a fully operational research infrastructure, with its core value-added capabilities contributing to related strategic objectives, as it follows.

Access provision. Centrally managed access to four platforms (ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB) provides seamless use of integrated stationary and mobile world-class laboratories, resources and data. Coupled with highly qualified expertise, it fosters excellence-driven research and innovative practices and interventions across academia, heritage sectors, and industry.

Bridging disciplines for innovation. E-RIHS integrates world-leading EU facilities and diverse disciplines to create innovative frameworks that transcend traditional boundaries. The objective is to unify diverse capacities into a unique and recognized organization that overcomes fragmentation and maximises the effectiveness and impact of heritage science.

Training and capacity building. Through its HS Academy, E-RIHS delivers vanguard, highly specialised training to equip students, researchers, and professionals with advanced interdisciplinary skills and knowledge. The objective is to enable the next generation of heritage scientists to take full advantage of E-RIHS access services.

Research and development. Co-creation processes that combine needs, expertise and resources to develop innovative analytical tools and new methods. The objective is to enhance and expand E-RIHS service provision and to ensure that E-RIHS remains at the forefront of addressing evolving challenges in heritage science.

Open science. Interoperable ecosystems of tools and data to promote collaboration and transparency in the processes and outcomes and ensure that data are aligned with FAIR principles and the *European Open Science Cloud* (EOSC). The objective is to enable open access in heritage science, maximize the value of research outputs and foster interdisciplinary advancements.

Best practices and standards. Identification, development and standardization of common and best practices across the heritage science community. The objective is to establish a cohesive framework that enhances the efficiency and impact of collaborative efforts.

Community engagement and outreach. Engagement with diverse audiences, including the general public and policy makers, through citizen science and targeted initiatives. The objective is to amplify public awareness, inform policymaking and maximise the scientific, societal, and economic value of heritage science in society.

International collaboration. Global partnerships to enlarge E-RIHS reach, engage untapped capacities and strengthen its leadership in heritage science. The objective is to unite diverse international communities, exchange and promote shared solutions, and position heritage science as a means of cultural and scientific diplomacy to enhance global understanding and drive progress.

1.3 THE CONTEXT

1.3.1 The Lead-up to ERIC

E-RIHS stems from a series of research projects supported by the *European Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation* (FP) since 1999. It has also benefited from national (e.g., Italy, Portugal, Slovenia) and regional initiatives (e.g., Latium Region, Italy), funded through direct contributions or competitive programmes under the *European Structural and Investment Funds* (ESIF) to implement *Smart Specialization Strategies* (S3). These initiatives have been instrumental in shaping and advancing the lifecycle stages of E-RIHS, from conceptualization to operational phase.

The E-RIHS **concept** originated in the Labs TECH network (FP5, 1999–2002), highlighting the need for shared expertise, resources, and technologies for cultural heritage. Eu-ARTECH (FP6, 2004–2009) formalized this vision by introducing the ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB access platforms. CHARISMA (FP7, 2009–2014) expanded the consortium and strengthened these efforts. The **design** phase, advanced by IPERION CH (H2020, 2015–2019), secured E-RIHS’s inclusion in the ESFRI Roadmap 2016. It also explored synergies with ARIADNE (FP7, 2013–2017), ARIADNE+ (H2020, 2019–2022), PARTHENOS (H2020, 2015–2019), and SSHOC (H2020, 2019–2022) to shape DIGILAB, E-RIHS’s fourth platform. The **preparation** was undertaken through E-RIHS PP (H2020, 2017–2020), laying the foundation for the ERIC. The **implementation**, supported by E-RIHS IP (HEU, 2022–2024), focused on legal and operational readiness for ERIC, while IPERION HS (H2020, 2020–2024) supported infrastructure activities.

ERIC step 1 was submitted in February 2021, step 2 in March 2023, with the implemented version finalized in April 2024. The EC decision on ERIC approval is expected in early 2025, marking the transition to the **operational** phase.

Figure 1: RI lifecycle of E-RIHS.

1.3.1 Contribution to European Policies and Priorities

Establishing a cohesive **heritage science ERA** has long been one of the core goals of the E-RIHS ERIC community. With its pan-European reach and extensive consortium of partner institutions, E-RIHS ERIC serves as a key enabling initiative contributing to European policies. Formally part of the SSH ESFRI domain, E-RIHS is also firmly embedded into Physical Sciences domain, supporting a wide range of European policies and priorities.

Through the EU R&I framework programmes, E-RIHS enhances research capacity by accelerating outcomes in excellent science (e.g., ERC, MSCA), collaborative projects (e.g., clusters, particularly Cluster 2 *Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society* and *Widening Participation*), and industrial competitiveness (e.g., *EIC Culture and Creativity*). E-RIHS also transforms research into actionable societal solutions, acting as a player in framework programmes like Creative Europe and Digital Europe.

On the **international level**, the Salvador da Bahia Declaration of the G20 Ministers of Culture¹⁰ emphasizes fostering international collaboration to support sustainable cultural policies and global heritage efforts. It highlights the importance of sharing expertise and research, aligning with the vision and mission of E-RIHS.

On the **European level**, E-RIHS supports the delivery of flagship EU strategies, such as the *New European Bauhaus*, as cultural heritage bridges people and their living environment with their cultural heritage. The *European Green Deal*, particularly its key initiative the Renovation Wave aims to double the annual energy renovation rates in 10 years to also enhance the quality of life for people using the buildings, 35% of which are older than 50 years, many of which are protected as cultural heritage. E-RIHS ERIC will contribute to the understanding of the built heritage environment, ensuring that interventions proceed in accordance with its extraordinary heritage values.

The *EU Work Plan for Culture 2023–2026*¹¹ outlines four priority areas promoting the impact of cultural heritage on people of all ages and backgrounds, enhancing people’s quality of life, and improving the health and overall well-being of individuals and communities. The E-RIHS mission and vision are aligned with the priority areas, which makes E-RIHS ideally positioned to support the delivery of the Work Plan, be it through empowered cultural and creative sectors, enhanced cultural participation, strengthened resilience and sustainability, and cultural diplomacy.

E-RIHS scientific strategy is also aligned with the complementary policies linked to the digital domain, including the *European data space for cultural heritage*.¹² By incorporating digital technologies into research, documentation, and engagement, and by developing capacity and infrastructure, E-RIHS contributes to digital transformation of the heritage sector. This is ensured by

¹⁰ G20 Ministers of Culture. (2024). *Salvador da Bahia Declaration of the G20 Ministers of Culture, 8th November 2024*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.br/cultura/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/declaracao-de-salvador-da-bahia-e-adotada-durante-reuniao-ministerial/CWGSalvadoraBahiaDeclarationMinisters08.11.2024.pdf> [accessed 6 Jan. 2025].

¹¹ European Commission. (2022). *EU Work Plan for Culture 2023–2026*. *Official Journal of the European Union*, C 466/01. Retrieved from [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022G1207\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022G1207(01))

¹² European Commission. (2021). *Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/1970 of 10 November 2021 on a common European data space for cultural heritage*. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 401, 3–10. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021H1970>.

the active participation of key E-RIHS institutional partners in the initiative to launch the *European Heritage Cloud* or *European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage*, where E-RIHS plays a pivotal role in the *European Cloud for Heritage Open Science* (ECHOES) project, the foundational digital infrastructure connecting other digital services and tools. As a unique and intensive generator of heritage science data, E-RIHS holds a distinctive position within the research landscape. This enables it to effectively team up with complementary infrastructures (e.g., CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS). These collaborations enable E-RIHS to strengthen its integration into the *European Open Science Cloud* (EOSC).

Furthermore, E-RIHS collaborates closely with the *Joint Programming Initiative Cultural Heritage and Global Change* (JPI CH), formalized through a MoU to strengthen cultural heritage research. E-RIHS is also active in preparing the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) to be published in 2025 under the *Alliance for Research into Cultural Heritage in Europe* (ARCHE) project, a key step towards launching the *EU Partnership on Resilient Cultural Heritage*.

On the **regional levels**, it is essential to stress the support that E-RIHS ERIC will provide to the delivery of the objectives of the *European Cohesion Policy Programme* and particularly the *Smart Specialization Strategy* (S3). Through investments into cutting edge infrastructure, S3 initiatives in some countries can be effectively implemented, delivering growth and jobs in public and private sectors supported by the *EU Cohesion Policy*. E-RIHS ERIC will also contribute to regional and international cooperation, bringing crucial international exposure to such cooperation, also through promotion of research activities in European regions and attracting investment.

1.4 SCIENTIFIC LEADERSHIP

As stated by the European Commission, advanced technologies and new scientific approaches greatly improve the understanding, preservation and dissemination of cultural heritage.¹³ E-RIHS exemplifies this by focusing its efforts on tangible heritage materials (e.g., artefacts, monuments, and archaeological sites) and linking their materiality to their broader cultural significance.

Despite global recognition of its pioneering tools and databases, European heritage science requires better structuring to avoid fragmentation and duplication. E-RIHS addresses this need by strengthening collaboration and fostering an innovative and cohesive research environment to maintain Europe's leadership in heritage science.

1.4.1 Heritage Science: Definition and Scope

Heritage science is the interdisciplinary domain of scientific study of heritage. *“Heritage science draws on diverse humanities, sciences and engineering disciplines. It focuses on enhancing the understanding, care and sustainable use of heritage so it can enrich people’s lives, both today and in the future. Heritage science is an umbrella term encompassing all forms of scientific inquiry into human works and the combined works of nature and humans, of value to people.”*

¹³ European Commission. (2014). *Towards an integrated approach to cultural heritage for Europe* (COM/2014/0477 final). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52014DC0477>.

This definition of heritage science was developed by the community in an open process mediated by E-RIHS with ICCROM in 2019. The need for this definition arose from the developments which, in a similar manner to environmental science, nascent in the 1960s and 1970s, are now leading heritage science to developing its philosophical and theoretical canon.¹⁴

In line with the heritage science definition, the research questions addressed by E-RIHS concern the past, present and future of heritage:

- **The past:** Investigating the origins, historical contexts, and cultural values of heritage;
- **The present:** Diagnosing the current state of heritage, the factors influencing its condition, and understanding its meanings and values for contemporary society;
- **The future:** Innovating care, conservation and transmission methods to safeguard heritage and convey narratives of its layered and dynamic significance to future generations.¹⁵

1.4.2 Challenges and Opportunities

Knowledge Co-creation. Scientific challenges arise from the intersection of humanities, sciences, traditional crafts and the expertise of cultural heritage professionals. It results in researchers from various disciplines working together and combining academic expertise with the knowledge of professionals and artisans. This interdisciplinary approach fosters new paradigms that combine hard sciences, humanities and other professional expertise, collaborating with equal roles and importance to advance cultural heritage research and practices.

From Understanding the Past of Heritage to Shaping Its Future. The origin of material heritage, where and when it was made, its use and history, method of manufacture, circulation and trade, as well as cultural, symbolic and other values it embodies, are at the crux of heritage science research, enabling its deeper understanding and better interpretation. Further key questions address alteration over time, the diagnosis of current state, their future and the way we care about cultural heritage for the benefit of generations to come.

Harnessing Collaboration to Bridge Object- and Problem-Driven Research. Millions of objects from the outstanding European collections, thousands of sites, monuments and buildings are our research cases, requiring scientific examination, novel interpretation and improved preservation. Responding to these needs requires both detailed analytical campaigns and large-scale collaborative projects. E-RIHS fosters coordinated efforts across research laboratories and cultural institutions from all over Europe and beyond to meet these needs and seamlessly integrate object-driven and problem-driven research approaches.

Complexity of Heritage Materials. Heritage objects and sites are intrinsically heterogeneous and require cutting edge material science: they have been subject to ageing, use, and deterioration under diverse and often unknown conditions over many years, decades or even millennia. Cultural heritage materials are fragile: their integrity must be preserved, and their safety must be guaranteed throughout the scientific process, from sampling to analytical protocols, using a well-defined, consistent risk management process to minimize the potential for loss or damage.

¹⁴ From: Strlič, M. (2018). *Heritage science: A future-oriented cross-disciplinary field*. Angewandte Chemie International Edition, 57(25). <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201804246>.

¹⁵ E-RIHS. (2022). *E-RIHS Scientific and Technical Description (STD) (v5.02)*. European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

Science for the Benefit of Humanity. Research questions in heritage science are fundamentally driven by humanities disciplines. Increasing knowledge and improved interpretation of heritage enhances public engagement and access, promotes community participation and enhances social and territorial cohesion, while fostering respect for diversity. These principles communicate our European values, strengthening the role of culture and cultural heritage in EU external relations.

1.4.3 The Core Values

Scientific strategy of E-RIHS builds upon ten core values:

1. **Competencies** are at our core and skills are central to our values system.
2. **Interdisciplinarity** of our teams involving complementary cultures and practices.
3. **Co-creation** involving balanced contributions to knowledge creation from all involved.
4. **Engagement** with the public-facing heritage institutions for the benefit of citizens.
5. **Excellence** supporting outstanding projects.
6. **Interoperability** that promotes intelligent instruments, data sharing, and open access.
7. **Innovation** stimulating continuous evolution of heritage science.
8. **International recognition** underpinning global collaboration.
9. **Ethics** promoting respect for heritage values and encouraging responsible research.
10. **Quality** to ensure optimal user experience and satisfaction.

1.5 TOWARDS A GLOBAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Recognized since 2015 as a research infrastructure of global interest by the Group of Senior Officials (GSO) on Global Research Infrastructures (G-RI),¹⁶ E-RIHS is committed to fostering international partnerships through its dual strategies: the *Cooperation Strategy*¹⁷ and the *Enlargement Strategy*.¹⁸ The *E-RIHS Cooperation Strategy* emphasizes fostering collaborations and sharing best practices with international organizations and initiatives. The *E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy* serves as a framework for expanding the E-RIHS membership, establishing National Nodes, and formalizing agreements with non-EU countries.

Key collaborations underscore E-RIHS's global ambitions. In Egypt, Ain Shams University and Egypt Academy of Science and Technology are exploring the different options of formal collaboration with E-RIHS, and lead efforts to expand E-RIHS into the Arab countries such as Jordan, Morocco, Oman, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates. In the U.S., exchanges with institutions like The Getty Conservation Institute, the Smithsonian Institution's Museum Conservation Institute, The Metropolitan Museum of Art, and The Art Institute of Chicago, have been pivotal in building the concept of a G-RI. In China, joint laboratories are spearheaded by E-RIHS member organizations.

¹⁶ Group of Senior Officials on Global Research Infrastructures. (2015). *GSO progress report 2015*. Retrieved from https://www.gsogri.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/gso_progress_report_2015_final.pdf [accessed 1 Jan. 2025].

¹⁷ Castillejo, M., & Carmona, P. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D6.4 Report on Cooperation Activities*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11549463>

¹⁸ Ropret, P., Strlic, M., VIRGILI, V., & Lea, L. (2024). *D4.4 E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13483635>

A notable milestone is the signature of a MoU with ANTECIPA (*Associação Nacional de Pesquisa em Tecnologia e Ciência do Patrimônio, Brazilian National Association for Research in Technology and Heritage Science*), which builds on a three-year pilot with E-RIHS on open data exchange in Latin America and the Caribbean under the EU-LAC ResInfra project,¹⁹ and aims at establishing a framework for partnership with the E-RIHS ERIC. This MoU led a “Call to Action” to address cultural heritage damage caused by catastrophic flooding in Brazil in April-May 2024.

The participation of the intergovernmental organization ICCROM (*International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property*) as a perspective permanent observer of E-RIHS ERIC enhances the capacity of E-RIHS to integrate global stakeholders, reinforcing its role as a leader in international heritage science collaboration.

¹⁹ See: EU-LAC ResInfra, Towards a new EU-LAC partnership in Research Infrastructures (H2020: 2019-2023), <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/871140>.

2. E-RIHS SERVICES

2.1 USER ACCESS TO E-RIHS SERVICES

E-RIHS grants access to its services based on a detailed *Access Policy*.²⁰ Core principles of the E-RIHS *Access Policy* are inclusiveness beyond Europe, capacity building, scientific excellence and co-creation.

E-RIHS only accepts access requests that align with its mission and vision, falling within the scope of the interdisciplinary domain of heritage science. It supports a wide variety of crucial research questions, from focused studies of artifacts to large-scale, long-term projects. Its scope spans the examination of diverse heritage assets, including objects, monuments, and sites.

E-RIHS places users at the core of its mission. It serves a broad public and private community of researchers from many different disciplines, conservators, restorers, archaeologists, art historians, cultural heritage managers, and practitioners from museums and heritage institutions worldwide. The *E-RIHS User Strategy*²¹ ensures user-centric services by expanding the user base, gathering feedback, and integrating it into decision-making. Through community-building activities, regular consultations, and feedback analysis, this strategy enhances service quality, supports cutting-edge research to secure an access provision that adapts to evolving user needs, while upholding the highest standards of excellence.

Users can apply individually or as teams of researchers, professionals, and students. E-RIHS strongly encourages applications from teams with a strong interdisciplinary focus, not excluding teams involved in EU projects (e.g., ERC, MSCA) that would critically benefit from the diversity of E-RIHS tools and expertise.

2.1.1 E-RIHS Catalogue of Services and Platforms

The *E-RIHS Catalogue of Services*, available at <https://catalogue.e-rihs.eu/login>, details the full range of E-RIHS facilities available across the four integrated E-RIHS access platforms: ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB, which have been offered and improved over the past 20 years, and DIGILAB, which is still under development.

ARCHLAB provides access to physical and on-site digital archives, including datasets, reports, reference materials, samples, and unpublished grey literature housed in museums and research institutions. It supports research planning, data interpretation, and comparisons. Users benefit from personalized guidance by experts tailored to their specific research needs.

DIGILAB offers online access to heritage science data, complemented by digital tools within a collaborative virtual research environment. It provides services for sharing, curating, processing, visualizing, and ensuring the interoperability of data to foster data-driven heritage research. It offers

²⁰ Bertrand, L., Anglos, D., De Clercq, H., Castillejo, M., Spring, M., Charbonnel, B., David, S., & Dubray, F. (2020). *E-RIHS PP D9.3 E-RIHS Scientific Strategy (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4045832>

²¹ Heritage, A. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D5.8 E-RIHS ERIC User Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13624647>.

a cumulative knowledge base aligned with FAIR principles and EOSC, driving the development of emerging heritage digital twins.²²

FIXLAB provides access to advanced large- and medium-scale stationary research equipment and associated expertise for the study of samples and movable objects. Instrumental for advanced diagnostics and archaeometry, it enables high-resolution micro-analysis and cutting-edge imaging tools, supporting investigations into artefact origins, manufacturing, alterations, and preservation.

MOLAB is a mobile laboratory providing non-invasive, multi-technique diagnostics of fragile and immovable heritage assets, including artworks, monuments, and sites. Supported by expert staff, it enables in situ analysis for assessing conservation needs, testing preservation strategies, monitoring treatments, and advancing studies in art history and archaeology.

All platforms comply with the *E-RIHS Quality System*,²³ ensuring reliability, efficiency, and continuous improvement to uphold research excellence and effectively meet user needs.

2.1.1 Access Modes

E-RIHS provides a range of structured access modes, each designed to meet specific research needs and support diverse user communities. They are:

Excellence-Driven Access: Primarily applicable to ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB, this mode prioritizes proposals based on scientific evaluation, assessed by an independent Peer Review Panel (PRP). Proposals undergo technical feasibility checks by facility experts before evaluation by the PRP. Figure 2 details the excellence-driven access procedure.

Wide Access: Focused on DIGILAB, this mode ensures open digital access to heritage science data and services. While most data and tools are openly accessible, some resource-intensive services may require a peer-review process or restricted access due to copyright or ethical considerations.

Market-Driven Access: Access mode tailored to private sector stakeholders on a fee-for-service basis. Its scope remains limited, adhering to ethical and regulatory frameworks to ensure alignment with E-RIHS's non-profit scientific mission (currently in planning stages).

Matchmaking Services: Tailored to the needs of small cultural institutions, this mode facilitates connection between users and facilities through National Nodes, supporting routine analysis, capacity building and preparatory studies for research-driven projects (currently in planning stages).

Thematic Calls for Access: This mode is designed to address critical heritage science challenges. It aims to tackle pressing issues identified by E-RIHS (e.g., climate change), including those highlighted by the European Partnership for Resilient Cultural Heritage, ERC and MSCA projects (currently in planning stages).

²² De Luca, L., & Guillem, A. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D5.1 DIGILAB Implementation Plan*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13622848>

²³ Doherty, B., Andrews, M., & Virgili, V. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14546122>

Figure 2: Excellence-driven access procedure for ARCHLAB, MOLAB and FIXLAB.

2.1.1 Access Procedures

E-RIHS offers streamlined access through an online single-entry point, with the Catalogue of Services complemented by the Dashboard and the User Helpdesk. The CoS allows users to efficiently explore and select resources tailored to their research needs. The Dashboard simplifies the management of proposals, ensuring a user-friendly process from submission to evaluation. The Helpdesk provides tailored assistance, addressing user queries and providing step-by-step guidance from proposal elaboration to data management and result dissemination to ensure smooth access and facilitate user experience.

Access is granted to users worldwide, with priority given to those from Member States and Associated Countries. Discussions are ongoing to determine specific quotas per country and consider prioritizing E-RIHS ERIC members. Quotas for Third-Country users are established and published before each call, based on decisions by the ERIC's governing bodies and partnership agreements.

No submission fee is charged and although E-RIHS strives to offer free access where feasible, users may need to bear costs for travel, accommodation, insurance, and in some case access service. For ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB, travel costs may be covered if certain excellence conditions are met, subject to budget availability.

E-RIHS adopts an open access policy through DIGILAB for data and metadata generated by its access platforms. Embargoes may apply, but the primary aim is to ensure these outputs enrich the DIGILAB knowledge base and advance heritage science research.

Publications resulting from E-RIHS access must acknowledge E-RIHS support and accessed facilities and be made available in open access.

2.1.1 The Extent and Ambitions of E-RIHS Access

The extent of E-RIHS access provision is determined by the offer defined by each National Node. Based on the current scenario of ERIC members, E-RIHS ERIC is expected to provide access to over 30 facilities and 140 techniques and archives, complemented by additional virtual access through DIGILAB. It is estimated that E-RIHS will serve 300 users annually during its initial phase, with plans to increase this number to 450 and eventually 650 users as E-RIHS services become fully operational. With the integration of extensive digital access capabilities via DIGILAB, the total number of users served annually could potentially reach 1,000.

2.2 CAPACITY BUILDING: HS ACADEMY TRAINING OFFER

E-RIHS has developed its own dedicated *Training Strategy*,²⁴ designed to deliver a broad range of interdisciplinary skills, from engineering to digital, from physical sciences to humanities. The purpose of the strategy is to foster a successful learning and research environment within E-RIHS as well as through formal engagement of E-RIHS in the delivery of higher education curricula, professional training and lifelong learning. This approach supports the core aims of E-RIHS, from engagement and dissemination to research excellence and innovation.

The portfolio of training and education activities in E-RIHS is represented by its flagship activity, the HS Academy, encompassing:

- (i) Training organized by E-RIHS where there are gaps in the current training offer,
- (ii) A network of institutions from within the E-RIHS ecosystem, delivering heritage science training and education programmes, and
- (iii) A self-reinforcing community of E-RIHS alumni with unique and competitive heritage science skills.

The HS Academy provides an overarching platform for the delivery of doctoral summer schools, onsite training camps, webinars and lecture series, and HS training modules.

The primary aim of the *Training Strategy* is to ensure the creation of training experiences that enrich the quality and pushes the boundaries of collaborative heritage science research without encroaching on established delivery of formal training. E-RIHS delivers the strategy through the interconnected objectives:

- To identify and promote a set of core heritage science skills necessary to deliver E-RIHS excellence;
- To create a culture of interdisciplinary research and leadership;
- To embed continuous learning across E-RIHS and drive the development of future-proof skills in a complex, rapidly changing research field;
- To build around E-RIHS a competency-based alumni network;
- To ensure access to state-of-the-art training opportunities through diverse delivery methods.

Our core training focus is to promote the development and delivery of the necessary skills, understanding and knowledge base for the creation, implementation, and innovation in E-RIHS as a joint responsibility of all stakeholders, i.e., users, providers, and managers of the research infrastructure. By creating an appropriately trained and diverse heritage science community, we will ensure that the opportunities provided by the E-RIHS infrastructure are taken up in the most efficient and advantageous manner so that it continues to provide the full range of benefits to the society.

²⁴ Andrews, M., & Grau-Bove, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D4.5 Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13148658>

2.3 DATA POLICY AND IMPLEMENTATION

E-RIHS is committed to open data as stated in its *Data Management Policy*.²⁵ This commitment is operationalized through a comprehensive *Data Management Plan* (DMP).²⁶ The DMP ensures proper data handling throughout its lifecycle, from collection to preservation and publication. It aligns with the *Heritage Data Reuse Charter*,²⁷ and complies with the FAIR principles, and GDPR. Collaborations with initiatives like the *European Open Science Cloud* (EOSC), its *Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud* (SSHOC) cluster, and the *European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage* (ECCCH) further align E-RIHS practices with the European open science ecosystem. The data produced is generally licensed under an open Creative Commons licence unless restricted by legal or ethical considerations. Key to the E-RIHS data policy, the FAIR principles are interpreted in the context of interdisciplinary needs of heritage science data.

The Catalogue of Services offers an interoperable, FAIR-aligned platform for accessing E-RIHS services. Meanwhile, HS Academy training resources are FAIRified to enhance their accessibility and reuse for the benefit of the HS community capacity building. In line with open science principles, E-RIHS has established the Heritage Science Gateway on OpenAIRE to enhance global data visibility, a Zenodo community for open-access data sharing, GitHub for tool development, and E-RIHS.io to create a unified digital identity for its outputs.

DIGILAB is a key component of E-RIHS's data policy, designed to manage, share, and enable the creation of new knowledge from data produced by ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB. Its conceptual model ensures seamless dataflow, linking "research questions > methods > instruments > data production > analysis and interpretation > knowledge." By integrating a Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and a robust knowledge base, DIGILAB supports collaborative research and the co-creation of heritage-related knowledge. It leverages heritage digital twin concept to offer cutting-edge data-driven services that ensure E-RIHS remain at the forefront of the digital transition. National projects (e.g., HESCIDA in Belgium, ESPADON in France, H2IOSC in Italy, AID HCH in Slovenia) contribute to its development by integrating local resources to foster the growth of the E-RIHS community. The contribution of E-RIHS DIGILAB to the ECCCH will further enhance knowledge co-creation across different disciplines and heritage practitioners.²⁸

Looking ahead, the strategy is to deepen collaboration with SSH and complementary data-driven research infrastructures (e.g., CLARIN, DARIAH, EPOS, HERI, OPERAS), work with ECCCH to create an EU EOSC node for cultural heritage, and harness AI technologies to enhance data insights, streamline management, and build a dynamic knowledge ecosystem addressing global research challenges in heritage science and beyond.

²⁵ E-RIHS. (2024). *E-RIHS Data Management Policy* (v0.4). European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

²⁶ Padfield, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D5.2 Data Management Plan for E-RIHS ERIC*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12607922>

²⁷ Romary, L. (2018). *Cultural Heritage Data Reuse Charter: the Mission Statement*. Heritage Data Reuse Charter. Retrieved from <https://datacharter.hypotheses.org/77> [3 Jan. 2025]

²⁸ De Luca, L., & Guillem, A. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D5.1 DIGILAB Implementation Plan*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13622848>

3. E-RIHS MARKET POSITIONING

3.1 THE VALUE PROPOSITION

European research teams working in cultural heritage have pioneered the development of quality instruments, methodologies, and databases for a long time, in an independent, non-coordinated effort. About twenty-five years ago, the institutions now part of E-RIHS began reducing fragmentation, duplication, and isolation. Today, E-RIHS demonstrates that a structured approach adds greater value than uncoordinated efforts and sustains Europe's global leadership in heritage science.

The value proposition of E-RIHS lies in its ability to unite interdisciplinary knowledge, practices, and tangible assets under a coordinated framework, optimizing complementary expertise to serve the heritage science community. A dedicated *Marketing Strategy*²⁹ further amplifies the visibility and accessibility of its services, extending its impact.

Building on this foundation, the elements of E-RIHS marketability include:

- **Uniqueness of technology and service offerings:** A one-of-a-kind consortium that unites expert knowledge providers with cutting-edge research facilities, advanced digital resources, and collaborative environment.
- **Research driven by excellence:** A steadfast commitment to excellence, ensuring user satisfaction through high-quality Standard Operating Procedures.
- **Specialized support services:** Tailored services led by uniquely experienced heritage science teams, empowering researchers and practitioners to maximize their research capacity.
- **Advanced training:** Cutting-edge training programs designed to foster expertise in a field that is inherently interdisciplinary and intersectoral.
- **Centralized access:** A single-entry point for all E-RIHS services, offering visibility across every stage of users' access requests and research projects.
- **Open and FAIR principles:** Open sharing of best practices, recommended methodologies and unique digital heritage science resources; aligned protocols for experimental research practices and (meta)data archiving across Europe and beyond.

3.2 E-RIHS AS A PLATFORM OF INNOVATION THROUGH CO-CREATION

3.2.1 The Co-Creation Process

E-RIHS fosters a culture of exchange and cooperation in a safe and ethically responsible research environment. The combination of the skills and knowledge of the operators of the E-RIHS facilities with the scientific curiosity of its users naturally generates collaborative research endeavours and new collaborative projects for innovative results. The users' feedback is also an essential mechanism

²⁹ Nardello, I., & Virgili, V. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D4.2 Marketing Strategy for Boosting E-RIHS Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14513683>

to stimulate innovation in the E-RIHS service offer and in the effectiveness of its management practices. This co-creation practice is one of E-RIHS' basic paradigms for continuously renovating the value of E-RIHS for both the users and the providers of services, ultimately being at the heart of the RI sustainability, and keeping E-RIHS at the forefront of heritage science.

As a model interdisciplinary infrastructure, E-RIHS encompasses a variety of disciplines aiming to bridge between them towards the promotion of a culture of exchange and cooperation to advance science and to contribute to the development of new knowledge. Coupled techniques and data sharing and integration enable improved studies and understanding of heritage and heritage materials and will determine multiple collaborative opportunities. Historical and social contexts of heritage provide additional aspects of research to be actively supported, e.g., through DIGILAB. E-RIHS expects that interdisciplinarity will also foster new fields of research beyond heritage science, especially regarding instrumentation development, computing sciences, and the chemistry and physics of novel materials. E-RIHS also hopes to bring new inspiration to environmental and geological sciences, which have the study of the past in common with heritage science, and in all cases provide an exceptionally innovative ground for interdisciplinary research.

T3.2.1 The Strategic Framework for Innovation

The success and long-term sustainability of E-RIHS also relies on its capacity and means provided to unlock and manage its innovation potential. This is pivotal for the development and implementation of next-generation instruments, methods as well as knowledge and data to advance the state of the art across the RI and even redefine its research agenda.³⁰

The sustainability of E-RIHS depends on its role as a key research ecosystem innovator. The E-RIHS innovation framework provides a set of tools to achieve its goals and provides an interface between the scientific vision and the overall vision of E-RIHS tackling grand challenges in key areas of heritage science. This ensures that E-RIHS grows into a recognized innovation hub.

Various types of innovation emerge from E-RIHS operations, whether research- or use-driven, knowledge spillovers, technology transfer, clustering, or systemic approaches. This diversity stems from its broad interdisciplinarity, spanning scientific, technical, and academic areas such as diagnostic technologies, construction, cultural and creative industries, and tourism, while also advancing social, non-economic, and non-technological innovations. Here, 'industry,' a key player in innovation development, is broadly defined to include entities beyond academia with revenue or commercial potential, such as cultural institutions.

The *E-RIHS Innovation Agenda*³¹ drives the framework, using the so-called *Innovation Radar* to map innovation in (i) services in the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services with innovation or spin-off potential; (ii) research activities leading to new services; and (iii) outputs directly targeting key E-RIHS markets.

³⁰ Tehan, M., Corns, A., Anglos, D., Vopálenský, M., & Sotiropoulou, S. (2020). *E-RIHS PP D9.2 Analysis of innovation background (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946249>.

³¹ Sotiropoulou, S., Anglos, D., Castillejo, M., Corns, A., Gibson, A., Makridaki, M., Ropret, P., Teehan, M., & Vopalensky, M. (2020). *E-RIHS PP D.9.4 Innovation Agenda (2.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4288894>

It is complemented with an *Agenda for Smart Future Innovation*,³² which is a multi-level roadmap, aligning medium- and long-term E-RIHS priorities with funding opportunities across EU, national, and regional levels. It focuses on leveraging Smart Specialization Strategies (S3) to ensure long-term sustainability while addressing user needs and enhancing new and existing facilities of recognized excellence. Finally, the *E-RIHS Exploitation Strategy*³³ ensures innovation management by transforming research outputs into actionable solutions. In this framework, the Central Hub supports IPR management while safeguarding individual and organizational rights within the E-RIHS ecosystem.

The strategic innovation framework leverages the *E-RIHS Marketing Strategy* and its interconnection with the *Training*³⁴ and the *Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication*³⁵ strategies, ensuring a unified and effective approach that places stakeholder engagement at the center of E-RIHS growth. A stakeholder mapping for E-RIHS ERIC is provided in Annex I of *E-RIHS Marketing Strategy*.³⁶

3.3 MAIN MARKETS FOR E-RIHS

Several markets can effectively exploit the application of heritage science, leveraging advanced technologies and methodologies to enhance their operations, services, and engagement with cultural heritage. The following markets, explored in more detail in the *E-RIHS Marketing Strategy*, stand out for their potential to benefit from cultural heritage science applications:

- Conservation and restoration sector
- Museums and cultural institutions
- Education and academic institutions
- Architecture and urban planning
- Government and heritage agencies
- Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and international bodies
- Corporate social responsibility (CSR) and philanthropy
- Tourism and travel industry
- Construction industry
- Digital and media companies

³² Ropret, P., Carmona, P., Strlic, M., Anglos, D., Padfield, J., Targowski, P., Virgili, V., & Lazzeri, G. (2023). *IPERION HS D6.5 Agenda for Smart Future Innovation in E-RIHS*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10226726>

³³ Benassi, L., Manconi, S., Chaban, A., Carmona Quiroga, P. M., Castillejo, M., Silvia, I., Andrews, M., Fremout, W., Padfield, J., & Striova, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D6.2 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategy of E-RIHS ERIC*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10985840>

³⁴ Andrews, M., & Grau-Bove, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D4.5 Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13148658>

³⁵ Benassi, L., Manconi, S., Chaban, A., Carmona Quiroga, P. M., Castillejo, M., Silvia, I., Andrews, M., Fremout, W., Padfield, J., & Striova, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D6.2 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategy of E-RIHS ERIC*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10985840>

³⁶ Nardello, I., & Virgili, V. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D4.2 Marketing Strategy for Boosting E-RIHS Services*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14513683>

- Art market and private collectors
- Entertainment, and cultural and creative industries
- Publishing and media

In summary, multiple markets can exploit heritage science applications to enhance their services, preserve cultural assets, engage audiences, and promote cultural understanding and sustainability.

E-RIHS has a unique opportunity to position its marketing strategy within this realm of market possibilities. The likelihood of entering those markets should be tested with a mixture of avenues to be pursued: some bringing to the lowest-hanging fruits for immediate returns; some higher-road pursuits impacting on outstanding societal challenges.

3.4 MARKET TRENDS AND OUTLOOK

The integration of cutting-edge technologies into the field of cultural heritage presents exceptional opportunities for research, preservation, and promotion. Advanced technological tools, such as non-invasive imaging techniques, machine learning, artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) have transformed the way cultural heritage is understood, preserved, and experienced.³⁷

Research advancements: Technologies like hyperspectral imaging and deep convolutional neural networks are revolutionizing cultural heritage research, allowing for non-destructive analysis, helping researchers identify and understand the components and degradation processes of heritage.

Conservation techniques: Non-invasive technologies allow conservators to develop targeted preservation strategies. The use of 3D printing, or additive manufacturing, offers innovative solutions for creating replicas of damaged or missing components of heritage structures.

Interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation: Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-based devices encourage collaboration between researchers and stakeholders. Open-access repositories and 3D digital models facilitate group involvement, leveraging collective expertise.

Engagement and accessibility: VR and AR applications allow for immersive experiences of cultural heritage, not just visually, but also in tactile, olfactory and other ways. These technologies make heritage more accessible to diverse audiences, enhancing engagement and education.

Emerging technologies and future prospects: The adoption of AI and machine learning is gaining momentum in heritage science. These technologies make it possible to analyse large datasets, interpret complex patterns, and provide new insights into historical collections and environments.

The application of advanced technologies is reshaping the field of cultural heritage, providing new methodologies for research, innovative tools for preservation, and enhanced ways to promote and experience cultural assets. These insights provide a clear case for the sustainability of E-RIHS and its growth potential and can be regarded as the stepping stones of its marketability.

³⁷ Furferi, R., Colombini, M.P., Seymour, K. *et al.* The Future of Heritage Science and Technologies: Papers from Florence Heri-Tech 2022. *Herit Sci* **12**, 155 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-024-01248-8>

3.5 BRAND IDENTITY

The E-RIHS brand is defined through the following:

- **E-RIHS Corporate identity**, shaped by the actions of the research infrastructure, as well as through the values, mission, behaviour, and how it differentiates itself from other infrastructures. The corporate identity helps to build user loyalty, enhance reputation, create awareness, and underpins uniqueness. The corporate identity is shared by the E-RIHS National Nodes promoting consistency of the infrastructure as a whole.
- **E-RIHS Brand identity**,³⁸ defined through how E-RIHS communicates itself: graphical elements, narratives, slogan, media kits and similar, and includes the visual identity. The National Nodes have some flexibility for customization to better engage stakeholders, which includes using the national languages.
- **E-RIHS Visual identity**, represented by the visual elements defining the E-RIHS brand. These are tangible and are related to the visual and graphic aspects, in English language at the level of the ERIC: logo, brand colours and typography.

The E-RIHS brand, in its broadest sense, is one of the main assets of the ERIC and each action should be considered in relation to how it might affect brand appreciation. All externally visible work of the Central Hub is done under the E-RIHS ERIC brand including access offered in-kind by partners. The brand can only be used by partners that follow E-RIHS quality assessment criteria and provide suitable feedback to the E-RIHS ERIC on brand use. The E-RIHS logo has so far been registered by in the following countries: EU Member States, USA, Brazil, Canada, Mexico, Israel, Argentina, and Peru.

3.6 OUTREACH STRATEGIES

The outreach strategy of E-RIHS encompasses both communication and dissemination efforts, guided by the *E-RIHS Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Strategy*.³⁹ This comprehensive framework includes activities to raise awareness, engage diverse audiences—researchers, policymakers, and the public—and promote open science principles.

The strategy focuses on effectively sharing scientific achievements and outcomes, and fostering collaboration within the heritage science stakeholders. To ensure its effectiveness, progress is continuously monitored through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

3.6.1 Communication

E-RIHS communication activities are structured to actively engage the heritage science community, foster collaboration, and connect stakeholders through clear, impactful messaging. The slogan, “**E-RIHS | Connecting heritage to science**”, encapsulates the mission to bridge disciplines, making heritage science accessible and relevant to diverse audiences.

³⁸ E-RIHS. (2023). *E-RIHS Brand Guidelines*. Retrieved from https://www.e-rihs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/ERIHS_BrandGuidelines.pdf [accessed 4 Jan 2025].

³⁹ Benassi, L., Manconi, S., Chaban, A., Carmona Quiroga, P. M., Castillejo, M., Silvia, I., Andrews, M., Fremout, W., Padfield, J., & Striova, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D6.2 Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication strategy of E-RIHS ERIC*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10985840>.

The objectives of the E-RIHS communication strategy are:

- Support internal communications to strengthen the commitment to the research infrastructure.
- Create a collaborative environment at a global level for the protection of heritage.
- Strengthen the E-RIHS presence in the RIs environment and the E-RIHS cohesion in the heritage science community.
- Increase the visibility of E-RIHS by communicating scientific results.
- Enhance the impact of E-RIHS outcomes by disseminating and translating them into actionable insights for stakeholders, including practitioners and policy-makers.
- Engage the target audience and the public
- Involve users and new communities.

The E-RIHS communication combines the SMART strategy with the C-style: SMART standing for Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time-bound; C-style meaning a clear, coordinated, consistent and creative style.

E-RIHS communication is coordinated through a professional function at the Central Hub working with a network of communication officers from National Nodes, who translate materials into local languages upon request, ensuring consistent and inclusive messaging across all levels.

Table 1: Communication channels and tools to engage E-RIHS audience effectively.

Channel	Tools
VERBAL	Meetings, interviews (radio, tv), podcasts, conferences, exhibitions, fairs, roundtables, etc.
WRITTEN	Letters, reports, presentations, press releases, and newspapers.
VISUAL	Videos, photos, promotional materials (e.g., brochures, posters, cards, gadgets)
DIGITAL	Website, social media, emails, webinars, and newsletters, online meetings, videos, etc.

The E-RIHS website (www.e-rihs.eu) serves as the central platform for updates, resources, and stakeholder engagement. Complementary social channels amplify the reach and impact of E-RIHS communication:

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/e-rihs/>, setup to act as an E-RIHS user forum.

E-RIHS YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/c/ERIHSEU>, used to publish and share short videos created in relation to E-RIHS.

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/e.ri.heritage.science>, used for general dissemination and social engagement.

X (formally Twitter): <https://twitter.com/ErihsEu>, used for general dissemination activities and connecting with related projects and researchers.

3.6.2 Dissemination

The dissemination activities of E-RIHS are designed to maximize the visibility and impact of its research outcomes on various audiences in different fields, e.g., scientific community, cultural and creative sectors and industries, funders and investors, and society.

The key operational objectives are:

- To raise the awareness of scientific communities and stakeholders.
- To engage communities of potential users, through training activities and focused events.
- To enable mutual learning through exchange with other initiatives in the heritage domain.

- To maximise the impact of results in collaboration with users, stakeholders, the scientific community and the society.
- To promote open science practices to share data and contributing to interdisciplinary research.

The involvement of some of the globally most renowned heritage institutions within E-RIHS ERIC significantly increase the potential for impact, multiplying the opportunities for dissemination and engagement.

E-RIHS employs a variety of tools to ensure effective dissemination:

- **Open access publishing:** Encouraging publications in open access journals and the use of platforms like the Zenodo E-RIHS community for archiving and sharing research.
- **Heritage Science gateway:** A dedicated platform developed in collaboration with OpenAIRE to facilitate the sharing and discovery of publications, datasets, and research outputs across disciplines, <https://heritage-science.openaire.eu>.
- **Digital tools for data management:** FAIR-aligned data services, including GitHub repository, <https://e-rihs.io> collaboration platform, CORDRA metadata system and Opentheso vocabulary tool.
- **Training and events:** Dissemination through the HS Academy, which offers webinars, summer schools, and training camps to foster skills and share best practices.
- **Citizen Science:** Engaging the public in heritage science research through collaborative initiatives that empower non-experts to contribute to data collection, documentation, and preservation of cultural heritage.

4. E-RIHS GOVERNANCE AND ORGANIZATION

4.1 THE E-RIHS LEGAL ENTITY

A European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is an international organization under EU law, established through Council Regulation (EC) 723/2009, amended by Council Regulation (EU) 1261/2013. ERICs are created by European Commission decisions, requiring commitments from Member States or Associated Countries. This legal framework supports research infrastructures operating under the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).

E-RIHS ERIC, hosted by Italy, is recognized as an international organization for VAT, excise duties, and public procurement rules. While dedicated to non-profit scientific activities, it allows limited economic activities. E-RIHS operates through a distributed structure, with the ERIC providing central services and coordination among National Nodes. These Nodes, often legally autonomous, formalize their relationships with the ERIC via Service Level Agreements (SLA).⁴⁰

Although E-RIHS ERIC has no direct authority over Nodes, its mission and quality standards are upheld through commitments by all Nodes, the Committee of National Nodes, and the General Assembly, ensuring alignment and cohesion.

4.2 THE GENERAL STRUCTURE OF E-RIHS

4.2.1 The Distributed Structure

E-RIHS ERIC operates under a distributed structure defined by two levels:

- (1) The **Central Hub** serves as the legal seat and primary access point to the infrastructure. It coordinates the activities of the ERIC and provides centralized support for its operations;
- (2) The **National Nodes** operate within diverse legal frameworks, representing partner providers and coordinating national-level facilities and activities to align with the E-RIHS overarching goals.

E-RIHS ERIC operates in accordance with its *Statutes*⁴¹ and *Rules of Procedure*,⁴² which together establish the legal and operational framework of the consortium. The *Statutes* define the foundational principles, structure, and responsibilities, while the *Rules of Procedure* outline the practical mechanisms for governance and operations.

⁴⁰ Petitcol, R., Cazenave, E., & Graber-Soudry, O. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.2 E-RIHS SLA Template*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14242512>

⁴¹ E-RIHS. (2024). *E-RIHS Statutes (v10.04.3)*. European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

⁴² Weterings, M., & Van't Hof, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.6 Updated E-RIHS Rules of Procedure*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14184748>

4.2.2 The Membership Structure

E-RIHS ERIC offers several categories of participation, open to EU Member States, Associated Countries, Third-Countries (accepting all the implications of the ERIC legal form), and Intergovernmental Organizations.

Members: Full participants with voting rights in the General Assembly. Members commit to a renewable five-year term, pay the full membership fee, and actively shape E-RIHS’s strategic direction. Those listed in the ERIC decision or joining within 18 months are Founding Members, with equal rights and obligations as other Members, while playing a pivotal role in E-RIHS’s inception.

Observers: This status is available as a pathway to full membership. Observers commit to a three-year term, renewable once, contribute 50% of the full membership fee, and participate in the General Assembly without voting rights. They can engage in discussions, participate in E-RIHS activities and stay informed about E-RIHS developments.

Permanent Observers: Entities that foresee long-term participation but are not in the position to meet full membership requirements. Granted exceptionally by the General Assembly, they share Members’ rights and obligations, excluding voting rights. They contribute to E-RIHS’s goals and foster sustained collaboration.

Members, Observers, including Permanent Observers, appoint up to two representatives to the **E-RIHS ERIC General Assembly** from an appropriate national body or organization. Intergovernmental organizations represent themselves, and their involvement is agreed on a case-by-case basis.

Figure 3: Governance structure of E-RIHS ERIC.

4.2.3 Current Membership Configuration and the Central Hub

The **Central Hub**. Italy hosts the Central Hub of E-RIHS in Florence, at the Manifattura Tabacchi. This historic industrial site is part of an urban regeneration project led by art and creativity. The Central Hub encompasses 1,000 square meters of space, made available rent-free through a public-private partnership involving the National Research Council of Italy (CNR) and the Fondazione CR Firenze.

The current configuration of E-RIHS membership is as follows.

The **Founding Members**: Italy (Host Country), Cyprus, France, Hungary, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, and the United Kingdom.

The prospective **Permanent Observer**: ICCROM, International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property.

Node	Namespace	Website
IT	e-rihs.it	www.e-rihs.it
FR	e-rihs.fr	www.erihs.fr
HU	e-rihs.hu	https://e-rihs.hu
MT	e-rihs.mt	https://erihs.gov.mt
NL	e-rihs.nl	https://e-rihs.nl
PL	e-rihs.pl	www.e-rihs.pl
RO	e-rihs.ro	https://e-rihs.ro/
ES	e-rihs.es	www.e-rihs.es
SI	e-rihs.si	www.e-rihs.si
UK	e-rihs.uk	https://e-rihs.ac.uk
CY	e-rihs.cy	https://erihs.cyi.ac.cy

Figure 4: Website and map of E-RIHS ERIC Members (deep red) and countries involved in the Implementation Phase project but not yet part of the ERIC, with ongoing national efforts to join (pale red).

4.2.4 Expanding Membership across Europe and Beyond

Belgium, Greece, and Portugal played an active role during the E-RIHS Implementation Phase. Although their participation as Founding Members was not established at the time of ERIC establishment, efforts are ongoing at the national level to achieve this in the near future.

Similarly, Austria, an Observer in the Interim General Assembly, is advancing national negotiations to join E-RIHS ERIC as a Member.

Continuous efforts to expand participation in E-RIHS ERIC are led by the Enlargement Board (EB), engaging target countries such as Brazil, Czech Republic, Denmark, Egypt, Germany, Norway, the United Arab Emirates, and the USA. Established under the E-RIHS Implementation Phase project, its continuation as an ad hoc committee is subject to General Assembly approval.

The ambition of E-RIHS to establish a global research infrastructure dictates full engagement with non-EU and associated countries. Non-EU countries that are able to accept all the implications of the ERIC legal form, may formalize their membership in the ERIC. This is normally achieved through negotiation between the ERIC and an appropriate governmental body.

For countries where formal membership is not possible, bilateral agreements may provide an alternative. These agreements are tailored on a case-by-case basis, considering the country's potential contributions, expectations and alignment with E-RIHS ERIC's objectives. This process is guided by the *E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy*⁴³ and the procedures outlined therein.

Significant achievements toward the E-RIHS's global reach include the signing of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with Brazil's ANTECIPA, fostering concrete collaborations and exploring pathways to ERIC membership. Additionally, Egypt, through Ain Shams University and the Egypt Academy of Science and Technology, is actively exploring collaboration options via bilateral agreements or ERIC membership and spearheading efforts to expand E-RIHS participation across the Arab countries, including Jordan, Morocco, Oman, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates.

4.3 GOVERNING BODIES OF E-RIHS ERIC

Within the scope and operation of E-RIHS ERIC, three perimeters can be identified:

(1) The **CORE PERIMETER** represents actions where E-RIHS ERIC is in full legal control and has full responsibility. It is defined through:

- Geographical area where the activities are developed under the full legal control of the ERIC.
- Instrumental resources: facilities and services procured directly by (or made available to) the ERIC, staff hired or made available.
- Support resources made directly available to the ERIC, either in-cash or in-kind and based on approved budgets and by allowing defined powers.
- Accounting and reporting in the budget and balance of the ERIC under the responsibility of the ERIC and possibly submitted to external audit or subject to a specific administrative/technical assessment by the ERIC Members.

(2) The **INTEGRATED OPERATIONS PERIMETER**, where the National Nodes act together as a joint facility and where the advisory boards as well as the independent auditors operate. It can be defined by:

- Catalogue of Services: the list of the facilities and related services available in alignment with the ERIC scope, but not under the responsibility of the ERIC.
- Overall value of the resources available to support these activities in the yearly general budgets and accounts (not audited but potentially assessed by the General Assembly through an internal committee).
- Activities and the estimated resources available in the yearly reports.

(3) The **IMPACT PERIMETER**, where the E-RIHS ERIC activities influence or are perceived by external stakeholders. It can be assessed through indicators tracing impact on, e.g.:

- Users: Numbers, nationalities, qualifications, and satisfaction, evaluated via surveys and feedback.
- Science and Scientific Communities: Contributions shown in publications, reports, and research outcomes.

⁴³ Ropret, P., Strlic, M., Virgili, V., & Lea, L. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D4.4 E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13483635>

- Economy and Environment: Effects at local, national, and global levels.
- Science and Cultural Diplomacy: Outreach initiatives beyond Europe.
- European Policies and Programmes: Contributions to e.g., the EU Green Deal, EU framework programmes, and partnerships like Resilient Cultural Heritage.

4.3.1 Bodies in the Core Perimeter

General Assembly (GA): The highest decision-making body, comprising Members (with voting rights), Observers, and Permanent Observers, overseeing E-RIHS strategy, governance, budget, and membership decisions.

Director General (DG). Legal representative and executive power of E-RIHS ERIC, responsible for implementing General Assembly decisions and overseeing scientific, financial, and administrative management of the ERIC, supported by the Central Hub.

The Deputy Directors. E-RIHS ERIC Deputy Directors exercise responsibilities related to specific areas of activity, through which they support the delivery of the ERIC policies and strategies, in close collaboration with the Director General and the Committee of National Nodes.

The Central Hub. Assists the overall implementation and operation of E-RIHS ERIC, supporting the Director General and ensuring efficient governance, administrative and operational functions.

4.3.2 Bodies in the Integrated Operations Perimeter

National Nodes (NN). They represent Members, by adopting any national legal structure, and coordinate partner providers, offering access to facilities under E-RIHS ERIC quality criteria. They sign Service Level Agreements with the ERIC, and may conduct independent activities, provided these do not use the E-RIHS label or impact its operations.

Committee of National Nodes (CNN). It is the scientific body of E-RIHS ERIC, composed of National Coordinators. Its primary role is to prepare the annual offer of the Catalogue of Services, ensuring alignment with ERIC's quality standards and policies. The CNN ensures that users are represented and advises the Director General. It contributes to the scientific strategy and advises the Director General on national-level needs.

Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB). Composed of internationally renowned experts, it provides independent advice to the General Assembly on scientific priorities, ethics, user relations, and quality. Annually, it evaluates E-RIHS ERIC's activities and those conducted by Members under its label, ensuring alignment with strategic goals and ethical standards.

5. MANAGEMENT AND HUMAN RESOURCES

The Management and Human Resources framework of E-RIHS is shaped by the *Rules of Procedure*,⁴⁴ the *Guidelines for the E-RIHS Central Hub Management Practices*,⁴⁵ and the *Human Resources Strategy and Procedures*.⁴⁶

The *Rules of Procedure* serve as the foundation for E-RIHS's operational and administrative frameworks, ensuring efficient governance and compliance with statutory requirements.

The *Guidelines for the E-RIHS Central Hub* detail the organizational structure and management practices, emphasizing centralized coordination to ensure consistent quality and alignment across National Nodes.

The *Human Resources Strategy and Procedures* focuses on staffing models, recruitment policies, and career development, providing a transparent framework to attract and retain talent while supporting both central and national operations. This approach is critical for ensuring the delivery of high-quality services and fostering professional growth within the infrastructure.

Together, these documents provide the basis for strategic, operational, and administrative procedures that ensure effective management across the distributed research infrastructure.

5.1 CENTRAL AND NATIONAL MANAGEMENT

Effective management within E-RIHS ERIC relies on clearly defined responsibilities of key roles:

- **General Assembly Chair(s)** oversee the strategic decision-making body.
- **Chair(s) of the Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board** guide scientific and ethical evaluations.
- **Director General** leads overall management and implements the strategic objectives.
- **Deputy Director(s)**, if appointed, assist the Director General in specific functions.
- **National Coordinators** manage the operations of their respective National Nodes.
- **Central Hub staff** support the Director General in coordinating administrative, operational, and scientific activities across the infrastructure.

E-RIHS ERIC General Assembly appoints Director General, who exercises executive power. The National Coordinators manage their National Nodes, which have the flexibility to design organizational structures tailored to their national contexts. This decentralized approach ensures both alignment with E-RIHS objectives and adaptability to local requirements.

⁴⁴ Weterings, M., & Van't Hof, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.6 Updated E-RIHS Rules of Procedure*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14184748>.

⁴⁵ Striova, J., Benassi, L., Manconi, S., Chaban, A., Buti, D., Doherty, B., Petitcol, R., Cano, E., Ramírez Barat, B., Molina, T., Virgili, V., Van't Hoff, J., Mims, A., Grau-Bove, J., & Strlič, M. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.5 Guidelines for the E-RIHS Central Hub Management Practices*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14018055>.

⁴⁶ Virgili, V., & Colautti, V. (2023). *E-RIHS IP D3.1 E-RIHS ERIC Human Resources Strategy and Procedures*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8406431>.

5.1.2 Financial Management, Accountancy, and Control

The Director General, supported by the Central Hub, oversees financial management in compliance with the E-RIHS *Statutes*⁴⁷ and *Rules of Procedure*. Key activities include:

- **Annual budget.** The Director-General prepares an annual budget, incorporating in-kind and in-cash contributions, aligned with the activity programme. Approval by the General Assembly is required.
- **Five-Year Financial Plan.** A strategic framework for sustainability and alignment with E-RIHS objectives, also approved by the General Assembly.
- **Financial reporting.** Annual financial reviews, including independent audits, ensure compliance with ERIC regulations and host country laws.
- **Transactions Oversight.** The Central Hub ensures the management and monitoring of financial transactions for accuracy, transparency, and accountability.
- **External Funding and Costs:** Oversight includes externally funded projects, personnel expenses, and travel costs.
- **Tax Exemption:** Management of tax exemption processes follows national and European regulatory frameworks to ensure compliance.

The General Assembly approves key financial decisions, including the annual budget, in-kind contributions, financial plans, and any changes to the financial model or policy. The Director General drafts financial rules, subject to General Assembly approval. The financial year runs from 1 January to 31 December, with an annual activity report submitted to the European Commission and relevant public authorities within six months of year-end and is a public document.

The **annual activity report** provides a comprehensive overview of the previous financial year. It may include:

- (i) Planned and achieved activities;
- (ii) Financial overview with detailed accounts of income, expenditures, and financial management;
- (iii) Performance evaluation using the KPIs defined in the *E-RIHS Quality System*;
- (iv) Outline of future plans.

Accountancy is subject to annual audits conducted by a certified compliance auditor. Payroll services are managed through outsourcing.

5.2 PROMOTING DIVERSITY, INCLUDING GENDER EQUALITY

5.2.1 Diversity, Equality and Inclusion

E-RIHS ERIC is committed to fostering a diverse, inclusive, and equitable work environment, as outlined in its *Statutes*, *Human Resources Policy*, and *Human Resources Recruitment Procedures*.⁴⁸ Discrimination based on gender, age, health, disability, ethnicity, nationality, religion, sexual

⁴⁷ E-RIHS. (2024). *E-RIHS Statutes (v10.04.3)*. European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

⁴⁸ Virgili, V., & Colautti, V. (2023). *E-RIHS IP D3.1 E-RIHS ERIC Human Resources Strategy and Procedures*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8406431>.

orientation, or political views is strictly prohibited. Recruitment processes are transparent and merit-based, ensuring equal opportunities for all. The organization prioritizes staff wellbeing and accessibility by creating environments that enable equal participation for all. Regular reviews and adherence to best practices reinforce a culture of fairness and inclusion across all operations.

5.2.2 Gender Dimension

The E-RIHS ERIC gender dimension is grounded in the *Gender Equality Plan* (GEP), currently under preparation and set to be adopted once the ERIC becomes operational. A gender lens is applied across all research activities to foster awareness of gendered innovation. Initiatives like the *International Gender Champions*⁴⁹ might be actively promoted, along with potential consultations with the *European Institute for Gender Equality* (EIGE)⁵⁰ to integrate gender considerations into budgeting, procurement, and other operational processes.

5.3 STAFFING THE CENTRAL HUB

E-RIHS staff matters are governed by the *Human Resources Policy*, which applies to all personnel of the distributed research infrastructure, whether operating at the National Nodes or the Central Hub, and to those working for or recruited to work within the infrastructure.

During the initial operational phase, the focus is on staffing the Central Hub. The Central Hub supports E-RIHS ERIC on two levels:

- **Operational:** Focused on user-facing activities, including managing access calls, user relationships, training, public engagement, international collaborations, and communication. These responsibilities are organized into key personnel functions, such as support for access, international relations, HS Academy, and communication.
- **Internal:** Dedicated to administrative and management tasks such as HR, project management, funding acquisition, quality assurance, risk management, legal affairs, and finance. These responsibilities are organized into key personnel functions, such as support for governance operation, access funds, quality, risk management, and administration.

The staffing needs and related budget for the Central Hub are planned by the Director General and approved by the General Assembly. E-RIHS employs a range of staffing models, including employment contracts (permanent or fixed-term), secondments (paid or in-kind), and consulting. During the start-up phase, priority will be given to recruiting a small core team for critical roles in, e.g., administration, access, communication, quality, and legal matters. All recruitment positions are filled through competitive processes in line with the *Human Resources Recruitment Procedures*, ensuring transparency, merit-based selection, and equal opportunities. To optimize resources, secondments from member countries or the host institute, particularly as in-kind contributions, will be explored. Detailed regulations for E-RIHS ERIC employees are provided in separate documents, with *Staff Rules* under preparation and the secondment framework in draft form.

⁴⁹ International Gender Champions. *Homepage*. Retrieved from <https://genderchampions.com/> [accessed 6 Jan. 2025].

⁵⁰ European Institute for Gender Equality. *Homepage*. Retrieved from <https://eige.europa.eu/> [accessed 6 Jan. 2025].

5.4 STAFF TRAINING

E-RIHS ERIC staff are actively encouraged to pursue continuous professional development to enhance their competencies in their respective fields, whether scientific, administrative, or managerial. This applies to those working at the Central Hub, as well as partner organizations of the National Nodes, which are also encouraged to provide such opportunities. Dedicated training is provided as part of E-RIHS's *Training Strategy*⁵¹ to staff across the E-RIHS ecosystem to ensure they are equipped to address the specific demands of their roles within the infrastructure.

5.5 PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT

Performance management at E-RIHS ERIC involves regular assessments of staff. The General Assembly is responsible for assessing the performance of the Director General.

5.6 PREMISES AND FACILITIES

The E-RIHS ERIC headquarters at Manifattura Tabacchi in Florence provide modern, well-equipped spaces for the Central Hub's staff and visiting teams, enabling the organization of on-site international events and training activities in a dynamic, heritage-rich setting.

5.7 POLICY ON INSURANCE

E-RIHS ERIC maintains mandatory insurance for operational risks, including liability, employee compensation, property, vehicles, and professional liability, as determined by the General Assembly. Member, Observer and Permanent Observer liability is limited to their contributions, as per the ERIC Statutes. E-RIHS ERIC is not responsible for Partner or user liabilities unless required by Host Country laws, in which case its general liability coverage applies.

⁵¹ Andrews, M., & Grau-Bove, J. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D4.5 Revised E-RIHS Training Strategy*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13148658>

6. FINANCIAL AND FUNDING FRAMEWORK

6.1 OUTLINE OF THE BUSINESS MODEL OF E-RIHS

The driving principle of E-RIHS ERIC is sustainability, balancing the available resources with the cost of services, through continuous investment into cutting-edge facilities and excellent research.

E-RIHS business model is based on three types of financial flows:

- **Funding:** Public and private funds encompassing various forms such as fees for membership and services, payments, subsidies, participation in costs, grants, etc.
- **In-kind contributions.**
- **E-RIHS label:** Although not a financial flow in itself, it can create a leverage effect and lead to additional income.

As a distributed research infrastructure, financial flows within E-RIHS gravitate around two main poles: the National Nodes and the E-RIHS Central Hub.⁵²

It is to be noted that the double arrows in the figure above do not imply equal levels of financial flows.

Figure 5: E-RIHS business model and financial flows.

⁵² Petitcol, R., & Cazenave, E. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.3 E-RIHS Accounting Guidelines for Service Provision Costing*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14438974>.

6.2 CORE RESOURCES

Membership fees represent the monetary income contributed annually by Members and Observers. It constitutes the primary source of income for E-RIHS ERIC, ensuring financial stability to cover central services and operational costs. Revisions to fees are decided by the General Assembly, based on operational evidence, inflation, and evolving needs.

Host country contribution includes the statutory seat in Florence, provided refurbished and furnished, along with taxes and extraordinary maintenance, under an agreement between the CNR and Fondazione CR Firenze, with a nominal value of €100,000 per year.

In-kind contributions are non-monetary resources provided by Members to the E-RIHS ERIC. They include personnel time, facility use, materials, or other resources with a financial value, supporting the access services, operations, and governance of E-RIHS ERIC.

Service fee is a financial contribution made by individuals or institutions for accessing E-RIHS services, such as HS Academy initiatives or granted access provisions. If market-driven access is approved by the General Assembly, the ERIC may receive a share of revenues generated through National Nodes. The service fee never covers the full cost of the service, with the remaining expenses funded by E-RIHS ERIC resources or in-kind contributions by the National Nodes.

European project funding refers to research and development grants from European programmes that provide additional financial resources to support activities, such as development, joint initiatives, and operation of services at both the National Nodes and the Central Hub.

National/regional project funding refers to grants provided by national or regional funding agencies to support activities, such as investments in research facilities, R&D initiatives, operational, administrative and organizational costs of a National Node or its partners.

National/Regional/Institutional RI Funding refers to recurring or exceptional cash or in-kind contributions provided by national or regional authorities or partner institutions, aimed at supporting the operations and activities of E-RIHS National Nodes.

Philanthropic and sponsorship contributions refer to financial or in-kind support from private entities to sustain the E-RIHS's infrastructure, mission and operations. For example, the Fondazione CR Firenze contributed €10 million, in partnership with CNR, for the acquisition and refurbishment of the premises of E-RIHS's Central Hub and Italian National Node in Florence.

The description of each resource category is based on the E-RIHS glossary⁵³ and has been revised for clarity to ensure accessibility for a broader, non-technical audience. Some financing instruments have also been combined to streamline the structure of E-RIHS resources and align it with the budget lines provided by ESFRI as part of the 2024 Landscape Analysis exercise.

6.2.1 Annual Membership Fees

The annual membership fee is determined using a model that combines a fixed flat rate and GDP-

⁵³ The E-RIHS glossary is included in Petitcol, R., Cazenave, E., & Graber-Soudry, O. (2023). *E-RIHS IP D2.1 Draft of E-RIHS SLA Template (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8407328> and further refined in Petitcol, R., & Cazenave, E. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D2.3 E-RIHS Accounting Guidelines for Service Provision Costing*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14438974>

based component. The following formula is applied:

$$\text{Member Cash Contribution} = (\text{National GDP}) \times k + A$$

where:

- **National GDP:** The average value of the national GDP for the three years 2017—2019, as per EUROSTAT data
- **K:** A multiplying coefficient that sets a variable amount in relation to the country's GDP. The coefficient **k** is set equal to **0,0723 x 10⁻⁶**
- **A:** A fixed amount, equal for all members, set at € 35,000

Members commit to a renewable 5-year period. Observers contribute 50% of the fee they would pay as Members for a 3-year period, renewable once. The pro-rata annual contribution for the year of entry. The following table (Table 2) presents the membership fee for each founding member of the E-RIHS ERIC.

Table 2: Membership fee for each founding member of E-RIHS ERIC

Country	National GDP (M€)	k (x10 ⁻⁶)	A (€)	Total (GDP*k)+A (€)
Cyprus	21,721.2	0,0723	35,000	36,570 €
France	2,361,212.3	0,0723	35,000	205,830 €
Hungary	136,294.6	0,0723	35,000	44,860 €
Italy	1,765,801.0	0,0723	35,000	162,750 €
Malta	12,548.5	0,0723	35,000	35,910 €
Netherlands	774,126.7	0,0723	35,000	91,010 €
Poland	499,199.4	0,0723	35,000	71,120 €
Romania	205,202.3	0,0723	35,000	49,850 €
Slovenia	45,754.8	0,0723	35,000	38,310 €
Spain	1,203,626.7	0,0723	35,000	122,080 €
United Kingdom	2,434,466.8	0,0723	35,000	211,130 €

6.2.2 In-kind Contributions

E-RIHS relies on in-kind contributions from the National Nodes to efficiently adapt its services, enabling the integration of new tools and the removal of outdated ones without asset transfers or high costs. This approach ensures flexibility in meeting evolving needs. Effective implementation requires:

- Service Level Agreements (SLAs) to regulate in-kind services from a National Node and obligations for the ERIC to provide key central services;
- Accounting guidelines to ensure unified administrative practices for service costing;
- Tools to monitor quality and support reporting.

E-RIHS has defined in-kind contribution categories and criteria for accounting National Nodes' contributions to the ERIC, including:

- Reporting formats: From narrative descriptions to auditable financial values with supporting documents.
- Cost evaluation methods: Actual costs, unit costs, or fair market value.
- Frameworks for contributions: SLAs, ad hoc agreements, or no agreement.
- Use of contributions: Directed to the ERIC, external users, or both.

These criteria ensure systematic evaluation and clarity, as detailed in Tabale 3.

Table 3: Criteria for accounting the different National Node contributions to the ERIC.

IN-KIND CONTRIBUTIONS CATEGORIES		ACCOUNTING CATEGORY				TYPE OF COST			TYPE OF AGREEMENT			USE OF VALUES		
		Narrative	Indicative/ statistical	Declared	Auditable	Actual costs	Unit costs	Fair market value	SLA	Other agreement	No agreement	Internal use	External use	Mixed use
Goods	Durable				X	X				X		X		
	Non-durable			X		X				X		X		
Services	Access services	ARCHLAB			X		X		X				X	
		FIXLAB			X		X		X				X	
		MOLAB			X		X		X				X	
		DIGILAB		X					X		X			X
	HS Academy – training activities			X		X		X	X					
	E-RIHS scientific consulting	X				X					X			x
	Organisation of meetings or other events				X	X				X				X
	Travel of E-RIHS and National Nodes staff			X		X					X	X		
	Users travel			X			X			X			X	
Personnel	For the ERIC	With reimbursement			X	X				X		X		
		Without reimbursement			X		X			X		X		
	For a National Node	With reimbursement			X		X				X		X	
		Without reimbursement			X		X				X		X	

The E-RIHS validation process for in-kind contributions involves multiple levels (see Figure 6). At the partner level, contributions are first documented using E-RIHS accounting guidelines, with data collection and cost calculations performed internally. At the National Node level, contributions are centralized, verified against reporting rules and Service Level Agreements, and included in annual activity reports sent to the Central Hub. The Central Hub collects and monitors contributions, verifying their existence and requesting additional details if needed. It consolidates data into a draft report shared with the Committee of National Nodes (CNN). The CNN evaluates contributions for alignment with agreements, user demand, and scientific strategy, potentially forming ad hoc groups for this purpose. Results are sent to the Director General, who prepares the annual report for the General Assembly, which approves it by majority vote. The General Assembly also defines needs and strategies for the next five-year cycle, updating guidelines as required.

Figure 6: E-RIHS validation process of National Node in-kind contributions.

Over the years, E-RIHS has applied different models to estimate in-kind contributions from National Nodes. Two approaches were used: the first, based on historical practices from IPERION CH, estimated costs by extrapolating hidden contributions and scaling to E-RIHS Catalogue of Services; the second inferred values from expected access days and user demand. Data from the E-RIHS National Node Survey conducted in June 2023 provided actual figures, though they should be interpreted cautiously as they did not follow the accounting guidelines. However, all evaluations align in estimating, based on the prospective country composition, an annual in-kind contribution of approximately €10 million, fluctuating between €8.5 million and €11 million.

6.3 COSTS

The Central Hub and operational cost for E-RIHS ERIC include:

- Central Hub Personnel costs
- Travel expenses of Central Hub Personnel
- Fully serviced office premises

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- Service outsourcing (consultancies, payrolls, press services, etc.)
- Consumables
- Other/contingency & emergency management
- Access travel and subsistence
- HS Academy training events and conferences
- Communication services and materials
- Centrally funded initiatives

Table 4 provides the estimated unit costs for each cost category.⁵⁴ Adopting unit costs enhances clarity and reduces discrepancies during the estimation process. This approach also offers greater flexibility for modeling future cost scenarios.

Table 4: Estimated unit costs for each cost category of E-RIHS ERIC.

A	COSTS for personnel & ERIC base operation	Unit cost (EUR)
A1	Central Hub	
A1.1	Director General (1Y)	145,000
A1.2	Deputy Director (0.5 FTE x Y)	52,500
A1.3	Head of Office	97,000
A1.4	Officer (1Y)	81,000
A1.5	Assistant (1Y)	55,000
A2	Travel expenses	
A2.1	<i>Unit cost per mission in Europe</i>	700
A2.3	<i>Unit cost per mission out of Europe</i>	3,000
A3	Full serviced office occupancy	10,000
A4	Service outsourcing	60,000
A6	Other/contingency & emergency management	40,000
B	COSTS for additional operations	
B1	User travel and subsistence (average per user)	700
B2.1	Summer School (unit cost)	20,000
B2.2	Training camp (unit cost)	40,000
B2.3	User meeting (unit cost)	50,000
B2.4	Conference/seminar/workshop	
B2.4.1	<i>- in Europe</i>	25,000
B2.4.2	<i>- out of Europe</i>	50,000
B3	Communication services and materials (per year)	20,000
B4	Centrally funded initiatives (per year)	50,000

6.4 FIVE-YEAR FINANCIAL PLAN

The outlined financial plan covers a five-year period and relies on stable income sources (Table 4), derived from membership fees, alongside budget allocations to cover E-RIHS ERIC's fixed operational costs (Table 6). The E-RIHS business model is designed to ensure that the Central Hub's

⁵⁴ E-RIHS (2020). *Costbook (ver07)*. European research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

activities—critical to the ERIC’s operational framework—are fully supported through membership fees.

Additionally, the E-RIHS institutional partner community benefits from diverse revenue streams, including European, national, and regional competitive project funding, as well as recurring or one-time contributions to the research infrastructure. These income and expense projections for the Central Hub and National Nodes were estimated as part of an internal survey conducted in June 2023 and the ESFRI landscape analysis exercise in 2024. Their figures are not included in this document, as the standardized accounting procedures for the ERIC have only recently been established and will be applied once the ERIC becomes operational.

Table 5: E-RIHS ERIC income: Annual contributions per member for the first five-year period.

Country	Contribution type	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Cyprus	Membership	36,570 €	36,570 €	36,570 €	36,570 €	36,570 €
France	Membership	205,830 €	205,830 €	205,830 €	205,830 €	205,830 €
Hungary	Membership	44,860 €	44,860 €	44,860 €	44,860 €	44,860 €
Italy	Membership	162,750 €	162,750 €	162,750 €	162,750 €	162,750 €
Malta	Membership	35,910 €	35,910 €	35,910 €	35,910 €	35,910 €
Netherlands	Membership	91,010 €	91,010 €	91,010 €	91,010 €	91,010 €
Poland	Membership	71,120 €	71,120 €	71,120 €	71,120 €	71,120 €
Romania	Membership	49,850 €	49,850 €	49,850 €	49,850 €	49,850 €
Slovenia	Membership	38,310 €	38,310 €	38,310 €	38,310 €	38,310 €
Spain	Membership	122,080 €	122,080 €	122,080 €	122,080 €	122,080 €
United Kingdom	Membership	211,130 €	211,130 €	211,130 €	211,130 €	211,130 €
TOTAL		€ 1,069,420				

Table 6: E-RIHS ERIC expenditures: Operational costs for the first five years.

Cost item / year	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Central Hub	€ 736,731	€ 736,731	€ 736,731	€ 736,731	€ 736,731
User-related services*	€ 187,305	€ 187,305	€ 187,305	€ 187,305	€ 187,305
Outreach	€ 145,384	€ 145,384	€ 145,384	€ 145,384	€ 145,384
TOTAL	€ 1,069,420				

*for ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB, including user travel, meetings and training.

7. E-RIHS IMPACT

The provision of services for advancing heritage science is expected to produce distinct impacts. Some of them are direct as they immediately affect users, materialise in a relatively short-term and can be directly attributed to E-RIHS ERIC activities. This will likely be the case for scientific production and human capital formation, for example. In the short and medium term, impact at the level of policy shaping is also expected to be relevant, e.g., in relation to the preservation of cultural heritage, as a result of the science diplomacy activities that E-RIHS ERIC will conduct. Socio-economic impact, based on innovative products and services derived from the exploitation of the knowledge and experience generated by the E-RIHS activities, may materialize in longer time scales, including the possibility to deliver economic returns.

7.1 COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Based on the *Cost Benefit Analysis* of 2020,⁵⁵ we provide a modernized outlook of the estimated impact of E-RIHS ERIC, considered along three main impact areas, i.e.: the scientific, socio-economic, and societal spheres. From the analysis of 2020, we however retain that two conditions are key for the E-RIHS sustainability: the number of users at the steady-state and the degree of coordination and integration (added value) of services provided.

The E-RIHS access provision through a single-entry point is expected to improve the efficiency (in terms of time saved) and effectiveness (greater quality) of the research production in heritage science and related domains. Beyond purely scientific impact, the HS community will also benefit by human capital formation through HS Academy, through the employment and formation of specialized human resources, as well as with training events of external practitioners and students, including hands-on specialised training, either on-site or at large-scale facilities. The E-RIHS ERIC programme of outreach events and services will also be beneficial to the EU citizens as well as public administrations and operators, who will profit from non-technical knowledge, awareness and understanding of artistic and cultural assets, including those with potential tourist interest.

The costs of E-RIHS include investment and operational costs, i.e., all the outlays needed to operate and maintain E-RIHS ERIC throughout its life cycle. They encompass both fixed costs, which remain largely constant regardless of activity levels, and variable costs, which fluctuate based on operational demands. The Costbook of E-RIHS ERIC serves as the primary reference for calculating operating costs. If total investment and operational costs of E-RIHS ERIC are confronted with the expected benefits (impacts), the analysis indicates a positive Economic Net Present Value (ENPV) of EUR 11.3 million, meaning the benefits outweigh the costs by this amount when adjusted for the time value of money. Additionally, the Economic Rate of Return (ERR) of 6.02% reflects the annual profitability of the investment, while the Benefit/Cost ratio of 1.20 in the baseline scenario indicate that for every euro spent, E-RIHS ERIC generates 1.20 euro in benefits. Overall, the setup and operation of E-RIHS ERIC deliver a positive net impact on society by increasing the productivity of the heritage scientific community and contributing to broader economic and cultural benefits.

⁵⁵ Vignetti, S., Pezzati, L., Striova, J., Benassi, L., Bossi, M., Drdácý, M., & Dal Molin, M. (2020). *E-RIHS PP D6.1 Cost Benefit Analysis and socioeconomic impact assessment (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3946206>.

7.2 IMPACTS

Scientific Impact. As expected from an ESFRI research infrastructure, the main field of impact is science production within the heritage science community. Improved access to its platforms is expected to account for 75% of the total scientific impact (baseline scenario, 2020), increasing research output, availability, and reproducibility of results. E-RIHS also strengthens knowledge dissemination by producing high-quality scientific publications and citations, which contribute 25% of the estimated total impact. This improves the quality of research outputs and ensures broader accessibility to scientific advancements. The *E-RIHS Quality System* assesses scientific impact through publications mentioning E-RIHS, access demand, and the number of academic users granted access. To date, E-RIHS has documented 397 publications and 6,393 citations (Clarivate WOS, 1 December 2024) resulting from EU projects (EUARTECH, CHARISMA, IPERION CH, and IPERION HS).

Economic impacts. E-RIHS generates economic impact through innovation and knowledge transfer, benefiting practitioners and enriching the cultural sector. By translating research outcomes into real-world applications, E-RIHS equips practitioners with innovative tools and methods for the preservation, and appreciation of cultural heritage. This strengthens their capacity to address complex heritage challenges and enhances the overall quality of their work. Museums and cultural sites leverage the outputs of E-RIHS to innovate their processes, enrich their cultural offerings, and enhance visitor experiences. These contributions include the development of new narratives, advanced communication tools, and tailored services that broaden cultural engagement. Ultimately, the innovation driven by E-RIHS fuels growth in the tourism and education markets, creating tangible economic returns while promoting cultural value.

Societal Impact. By promoting a deeper understanding of cultural heritage that respects its cultural values and symbolic significance, E-RIHS fosters cross-cultural dialogue and contributes to science and cultural diplomacy, which may result in positive diplomatic relationships. The global reach of E-RIHS, supported by collaboration with ICCROM and its recognition as G-RI, is further strengthened by its advocacy efforts and participation in international events, positioning it as a powerful instrument for advancing cultural policies, diplomacy, and mutual understanding. E-RIHS also contributes significantly to human capital development, accounting for approximately 4% of the total quantified impact (EUR 2.7 million in the 2020 baseline scenario). The HS Academy plays a central role, offering training events such as hands-on sessions, specialized lectures, summer schools, and webinar series, which by 2023 have engaged over 2,300 participants and attracted 5,500 YouTube viewers. These initiatives enhance capabilities of young heritage professionals and scientists, preparing them to effectively take stock and exploit E-RIHS ERIC's advanced technological resources in their future careers. Public engagement and other effects resulting from dissemination and outreach activities also account for a proportion (4% for a value of EUR 2.9 million in the baseline scenario of 2020) of the total quantified impact. Further societal impact may include the contribution of E-RIHS ERIC to the analysis and preservation of the European cultural heritage, to policies and regulations in the field of heritage science.

Wider impact. The activities of E-RIHS ERIC have the potential to achieve wider impacts, in the long-term, by affecting markets and sectors more loosely related to the E-RIHS core activity areas. These impacts can be facilitated by E-RIHS ERIC but additional investments, activities, and actions from different stakeholders may be necessary to achieve them.

7.3 ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL AND GOVERNANCE (ESG) REPORTING

E-RIHS ERIC places great importance on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles, recognizing their critical role in supporting the *European Green Deal, Agenda 2030*, and post-2030 sustainability goals. To reinforce this commitment, E-RIHS plans to complement its financial and activity reports with a dedicated ESG report. The ESG principles are essential for the evaluation, monitoring, and reinforcement of E-RIHS sustainability commitments and for the creation of long-term value for all internal and external stakeholders, including users, providers, the public sector, as well as the private sector. This aligns with the *EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)*,⁵⁶ strengthened through our adoption of the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS).

⁵⁶ European Union. (2022). *Directive (EU) 2022/2464 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on corporate sustainability reporting (CSRD)*. Official Journal of the European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022L2464>.

8. IMPLEMENTATION

E-RIHS, recognized on the ESFRI Roadmap in 2016, is expected to become an ERIC in the first quarter of 2025, marking the start of its operational phase. The initial three years will focus on launching operations, followed by a transition to full operational capacity over the subsequent two years.

8.1 IMPLEMENTATION TIMELINE

8.1.1 Short-Term (1-3 Years): Establishing Foundations

Governance and Operations

- Establish E-RIHS ERIC and operationalize its statutory governance structure and policies to ensure full functionality.
- Constitute the Central Hub's staff, integrating personnel through recruitment and in-kind contributions, to form a cohesive and highly skilled team to coordinate operations.
- Establish Service Level Agreements (SLAs) with National Nodes to define operational standards and in-kind contributions.

Service Development

- Complete the E-RIHS Catalogue of Services, ensuring compliance with the quality system.
- Launch the first call for access to ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB platforms, ensuring compliance with the access policy.
- Develop and roll out training modules through the HS Academy.
- Initiate DIGILAB development with a focus on creating FAIR data principles and integrating existing heritage science data repositories.

Stakeholder Engagement

- Secure commitments to the ERIC from additional member and observer countries in Europe and strategic partners beyond.
- Strengthening collaborations with key European initiatives, including the *European Open Science Cloud* (EOSC) and the *European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage* (ECCCH)

Funding and Sustainability

- Prepare funding proposals to attract additional resources from European initiatives and similar opportunities.
- Enable E-RIHS services within the *European Partnership on Resilient Cultural Heritage* to enhance impact and effectively support cultural heritage communities.

Communication and Outreach

- Launch communication campaigns targeting the academic, cultural, and policy-making communities.

8.1.2 Medium-Term (3-5 Years): Expanding Capacity

Platform Integration and Services

- Fully implement DIGILAB as an integrated virtual research environment, offering advanced data analytics and interoperability tools.

- Expand the Catalogue of Services by integrating new providers, emerging technologies, and fully implementing the prospective access modes to address evolving heritage challenges.

Quality Assurance and Improvement

- Fully implement quality system with advanced metrics to drive continuous improvement, monitor impacts, and sustain E-RIHS leadership in heritage science.

8.1.3 Long-Term (5-10 Years): Enduring Leadership

Operational Excellence

- Achieve operational maturity through continuous workflow optimization and enhanced user experience.

Long-Term Sustainability

- Achieve financial stability through diversified revenue streams.

Strategic Growth

- Facilitate E-RIHS cross-sector influence beyond cultural heritage by fostering partnerships, enabling knowledge transfer, and leveraging targeted investments.
- Position E-RIHS as the global benchmark for heritage science.

8.2 IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY AND IMPACT

In 2026-2029, the impact of E-RIHS ERIC will be maximized through:

- Ensure a sustainable level of demand of access and services aiming at reaching the number of users of physical platforms as foreseen.
- Growth of E-RIHS ERIC within and beyond Europe.
- Increased collaboration with industry, e.g. the cultural tourism sector, the construction sector etc.
- Established collaboration with key sector initiatives such as ECCCH and *EU Partnership in Resilient Cultural Heritage*.

The implementation strategy and the impact of E-RIHS ERIC significantly depend on stakeholder engagement, among which are, principally:

- Users, prospective users and managers of cultural heritage assets.
- Institutions and bodies managing cultural heritage, e.g. heritage institutions, local authorities, and governmental agencies.
- Countries where membership or observership status can be pursued, as well as intergovernmental organizations.
- Non-EU institutions and interested in strategic partnerships.
- Other relevant initiatives (*ECHOES*, *EU Partnership Resilient Cultural Heritage*), projects (*ECHOES*) and infrastructures (e.g., CLARIN ERIC, DARIAH ERIC, CERIC ERIC, OPERAS).

E-RIHS, as the flagship research infrastructure for tangible cultural heritage and a leading producer of data-intensive heritage science content, will be instrumental in providing an interface between the cultural heritage community and the *European Open Science Cloud*.

8.3 QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Quality is one of the foundational pillars of E-RIHS ERIC, ensuring excellence in the services offered and alignment of activities with the mission and vision of the infrastructure. It is explicitly recognized within the *E-RIHS Statutes*,⁵⁷ as required by Article 7.3, which mandates a dedicated regulation for service quality standards and evaluation procedures, highlighting its central role in guiding the infrastructure's operations and standards.

The quality management system of E-RIHS, see *E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan*,⁵⁸ is designed to ensure operational consistency and foster continuous improvement, providing a robust foundation for scientific credibility and global impact. Its flexible approach accommodates the diverse operational contexts of National Nodes while maintaining adherence to E-RIHS's overarching quality principles. It integrates policy and operational procedures. The quality policy establishes the strategic principles and objectives, while the operational procedures provide the practical instructions and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to implement these principles.

The practical procedures provide a cohesive structure to assess and enhance quality across all activities and outputs associated with E-RIHS, including access provisions, training initiatives, and external endorsements. Providers and services undergo rigorous evaluation processes: prospective providers are assessed to validate their internal processes, governance structures, and technical capabilities, while existing providers and services are periodically reviewed against standardized KPIs to ensure compliance with established benchmarks. Feedback mechanisms form a critical component of the quality system, with user satisfaction surveys and performance reviews providing essential data on service delivery. These insights drive continuous improvement and align services with user expectations. Ethical guidelines are also included in the quality management system (see § 6.3 *Ethics Guidelines in Operations*) to ensure responsible operations concerning cultural heritage materials and data.

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) offer a structure for evaluating E-RIHS's operational effectiveness. Each KPI includes a clear definition, its ESFRI strategic objective, rationale, data sources, the responsible for data provision and collection, calculation methodology, unit of measure, frequency of assessment, and target values. Full details are available in the *E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan*. Table 8 gives an overview of the indicators and their corresponding targets.

Table 7: E-RIHS ERIC Key Performance Indicators.

INDICATOR	TARGET
FINANCES AND DEVELOPMENT	
1. Revenues	Assess target and actual values yearly
2. Number of members in E-RIHS	Increase numbers of formal engagement yearly
ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES	
3. Income from commercial activities and number of entities paying for service	Year 1-2: 2%; Year 3: ~5%; Full operations: ~10% of total revenue

⁵⁷ E-RIHS. (2024). *E-RIHS Statutes (v10.04.3)*. European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science.

⁵⁸ Doherty, B., Andrews, M., & Virgili, V. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14546122>.

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INDICATOR	TARGET
4. Share of users and publications associated with industry	Report when feasible
USER ACCESS	
5. Number of user requests for access	Full operations: 600 users/year for physical platforms; >100 applications/year; DIGILAB considered when ready
6. Retention of access users	Retain and steadily grow numbers after launch
7. Access demand	> 100% yearly across all platforms
8. Number of users served (and share per EU, non-EU country)	Initial operations: 300 users/year; Full operations: 650 users/year
9. Number of access provisions	100% fulfilment for the previous year
10. Access quality feedback	> 80% after the first 12-month probation period
11. Number of publications (open access and share per country)	1:1 ratio of publication vs accepted application; > 40% in open access, increasing yearly
12. Percentage of top (10%) cited publications	Assessable only 4-5 years post-publication
HS ACADEMY	
13. Participants in dissemination and education events	1000 participants/year for dissemination events; 84 participants/year for education initiatives
14. Hours of dissemination events	9 hours/year for dissemination events
15. Master and PhD students using E-RIHS	Target to be set after sufficient data collection
16. Training of non-E-RIHS staff	Target to be set after sufficient data collection
17. Educational/training quality feedback	> 80%
DATA MANAGEMENT AND DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE	
18. Number of available datasets (public and restricted)	Year 1: > 80% of dataset FAIR compliant; Year 3: 100% of dataset FAIR compliant.
19. Number of datasets used externally	Target to be set, refinement after test usage period
COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH	
20. Outreach through printed, broadcast and web-based media	Steady annual increase post-initial operations
21. Website and social media activities	Steady increase based on previous baseline data (2022-24): Website visits increased from ~59K/year (2022-23) to ~68K/year (2023-24), with an average session duration of 01:36 mins. Social media metrics include: Twitter 6.9K followers, YouTube 7.9K views, Facebook 7.6K post engagements, and LinkedIn 100K page reach.
22. Direct contact engagement (events)	Steady increase post-initial operations
SCIENTIFIC ADVICE	
23. Participation by RIs in policy related activities	To be set
24. Citations in policy related publications	Refinement after test usage period

8.3.1 E-RIHS Certifications

ISO-standard quality management practices and *Good Laboratory Practices* (GLP) are meant to guide an organization and ensure that the RI management and its facilities adhere to stringent quality standards in their operations. E-RIHS may acquire such certification once it is in operational phase, however some FIXLAB large scale facilities already hold such accreditations, which greatly enhances the value of E-RIHS to its users.

8.4 ETHICS GUIDELINES IN OPERATIONS

Ethics is integral to the operations and mission of E-RIHS ERIC, ensuring that all activities uphold the highest standards of integrity, fairness, and responsibility. Aligned with the *ALLEA Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*,⁵⁹ the *E-RIHS Ethics Guidelines*⁶⁰ provide a comprehensive framework to guide individual and institutional behavior. These guidelines are structured into four domains—individual, interpersonal, societal, and environmental—to address diverse ethical challenges across E-RIHS operations.

INDIVIDUAL DOMAIN. Values: Honesty, Integrity, Transparency, Reliability, Competence. The individual domain underscores the importance of honesty, competence, and integrity in all activities conducted within E-RIHS. Personnel and collaborators are encouraged to maintain a high level of professional rigor and accountability, ensuring that their research practices uphold transparency. This domain emphasizes the need to uphold academic integrity by avoiding unethical practices such as plagiarism, falsification, and data fabrication. Furthermore, meticulous documentation of processes and results is critical to ensure that research findings are reproducible and reliable.

INTERPERSONAL DOMAIN. Values: Respect, Inclusivity, Equity, Reciprocity, Sharing, Cooperation, Safety. It emphasizes fostering respectful, inclusive and collaborative relationships within E-RIHS and its broader community. Respect for people, equality, diversity and inclusion ensure that all individuals work in an environment of trust and mutual respect. Safeguarding policies ensure the well-being and safety of students, collaborators and E-RIHS teams (see also § 6.4 Risk Management). Professionals are encouraged to uphold ethical values in balancing professional competition and good research practices and are expected to share ideas openly, respect confidentiality, and recognize intellectual property rights. Practices such as peer review processes and acknowledging contributions promote fairness and transparency.

SOCIETAL DOMAIN. Values: Reputation, Trust, Stewardship, Service, Clarity. It underscores E-RIHS's role in bridging research and societal impact. The stewardship of cultural heritage values ensures that E-RIHS activities respect and preserve the significance of heritage assets. Responsible handling and sampling practices are guided by standards like the UK Institute for Conservation's

⁵⁹ ALLEA. (2023). *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023*. Berlin: ALLEA – All European Academies. DOI 10.26356/ECOC.

⁶⁰ Doherty, B., Andrews, M., & Virgili, V. (2024). Annex VI. E-RIHS Ethics Guidelines. In *D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan* (pp. 57-65). E-RIHS IP Project. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14546122>.

Ethical Sampling Guidance,⁶¹ respecting object value and ethical considerations, especially with human remains. E-RIHS prioritizes beneficence (do good), supporting public benefit. While its outcomes may aid authentication, E-RIHS does not provide authentication expertise. Data stewardship adheres to FAIR principles. Personal data is handled responsibly, complying with GDPR regulations. This approach fosters societal trust and safeguards E-RIHS reputation.

ENVIRONMENTAL DOMAIN. Values: Awareness, Efficiency, Sustainability, Protection, Innovation.

In alignment with the European Green Deal and the Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) principle, E-RIHS integrates sustainability into its operations and adopts eco-friendly practices to: (i) minimize the environmental impact of research activities, including resource use and travel—virtual meetings are prioritized to reduce travel emissions; (ii) promote efficiency and waste reduction across operations; (iii) advocate for environmentally friendly practices in the preservation of cultural heritage. By limiting its impact on climate, ecosystems, and biodiversity, E-RIHS ensures its research contributes to both heritage conservation and environmental protection.

8.5 RISK MANAGEMENT

E-RIHS ERIC has implemented a comprehensive *Risk Management Strategy*⁶² based on the international standard ISO 31000:2018,⁶³ which serves as the foundation for ensuring robust governance and operational resilience. The strategy includes a *Risk Management Policy and Framework*.

The *Risk Management Policy* outlines principles, roles and responsibilities at the different levels to support decision-making, as well as the ongoing maintenance, update and amendment of the risk management methodology.

The *Risk Management Framework* translates the policy into actionable processes. It organizes the risk management at three levels: Central Hub, which is responsible for managing risk affecting the ERIC as a whole, National Node, and individual partners. The framework establishes escalation and de-escalation procedures among these levels, allowing tailored responses to specific challenges while maintaining coherence across the organization.

The Risk Management Committee (RMC) oversees this framework. It is composed by the E-RIHS General Assembly chairperson (or delegated member), the Director General, a staff unit at the Central Hub with risk management functions, the administration staff unit, and additional legal, technical and insurance expertise co-opted as required.

In addition, the Central Hub maintains a comprehensive *Risk Management Database*, offering a detailed risk inventory, classified into potential impact categories as follows:

- **Financial risks**, affecting E-RIHS's finances.

⁶¹ Quye, A., & Strlič, M. (2019). *Ethical Sampling Guidance*. Icon Heritage Science Group. <https://icon.org.uk/groups/heritage-science/guidance-documents> [accessed 25 Dec. 2024].

⁶² Cano, E. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D3.3 Risk Management Strategy (1.1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10947670>.

⁶³ International Organization for Standardization (ISO), *ISO 31000:2018 - Risk Management – Guidelines*, available at <https://www.iso.org/standard/65694.html> [accessed 25 Dec. 2024].

- **Operational risks**, impacting provision of E-RIHS products, projects, and services.
- **Reputational risks**, concerning professional and scientific standing and credibility of E-RIHS and its community.
- **Physical and safety risks**, focusing on the safety and well-being of individuals.
- **Regulatory and legal risks**, arising from challenges in regulatory compliance.
- **People-related risks**, influencing corporate knowledge, continuity, professional development, and staff welfare.

This structured database ensures systematic monitoring and targeted approach to mitigate risks that could affect E-RIHS's objectives and operations.

8.5.1 Risk Management Plan: from the Implementation to Operational Phase

A detailed risk identification exercise was conducted to address the transition from implementation to the full operational phase of E-RIHS ERIC. Risks with medium to high likelihood are summarized below, along with corresponding mitigation strategies.

Among the **financial risks**, low support from prospective Member Countries, insufficient funding for transnational activities, and delayed or missed membership fee payments are included. Mitigation measures involve adjusting operational parameters to maximize membership, implementing temporary contribution measures only when strictly necessary and aligned with the Statutes, fostering EU-level advocacy to secure funding and to promote heritage science as a shared responsibility. Financial difficulties are further mitigated through the creation of a reserve and an emergency budget. At the national level, partner provider financial instability is mitigated by reducing reliance on single partners, avoiding over-dependence, and adjusting their in-kind commitments.

Operational risks include potential disagreements among partner providers and the E-RIHS ERIC Central Hub, mitigated through clear decision-making, fostering collaboration, and support from the National Coordinators' Committee. Service quality is ensured with strict criteria, performance monitoring, and a probation period (i.e., 12 months) for new partner providers before inclusion.⁶⁴

Among the **reputational risks** are a lack of collaboration with organizations not in the partnership, addressed through clear ethical guidelines and open communication, and limited stakeholder impact, mitigated by promoting the E-RIHS ERIC label, engaging policymakers, leveraging media, and reassessing outreach strategies.

This multilevel risk management approach implements targeted mitigation measures towards identified risks, safeguarding the reputation and operational continuity of E-RIHS ERIC while strengthening financial sustainability.

⁶⁴ Doherty, B., Andrews, M., & Virgili, V. (2024). *E-RIHS IP D3.5 E-RIHS Quality System Implementation Plan*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14546122>.

GLOSSARY OF TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Access. It refers to the use of a range of E-RIHS services and facilities, either physically, remotely, or virtually use of E-RIHS platforms and to offered services. It encompasses, but is not limited to, the use of advanced instruments, computing resources, specialized software, data repositories, data-communication services, sample preparation facilities, archives and collections. It also encompasses the set-up and execution of experiments, analytical services and expert support.

ARCHLAB (ARCHive LABORatory of E-RIHS). E-RIHS access platform that brings together organized scientific information in largely unpublished datasets from archives of prestigious European museums, galleries and research institutions (<https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/>)

B/C Ratio (Benefit-Cost Ratio).

Central Hub. Headquarters and statutory seat of E-RIHS ERIC, located in Florence, Italy (host country). It hosts the Director General and staff who support governance, coordinate activities, and oversee centralized operations and administrative functions.

CH (Cultural Heritage)

CNN (Committee of National Nodes). A scientific body within E-RIHS ERIC governance, composed of National Coordinators. It aligns ERIC activities with national efforts, serves as the main link to partners' facilities, and is responsible for preparing the annual service offer.

DG (Director General). The legal representative of the E-RIHS ERIC, responsible for the implementation of decisions of the General Assembly and for providing direction to the infrastructure. The Director General is appointed by the General Assembly.

DIGILAB (DIGital LABORatory of E-RIHS). DIGital LABORatory: E-RIHS access platform that provides remote access to heritage science data, supplemented with digital services and tools within a virtual research environment (under development).

ECCCH (European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage or Cultural Heritage Cloud)

EIC (European Innovation Council)

ENPV (Economic Net Present Value)

EOSC (European Open Science Cloud)

ERA (European Research Area)

ERC (European Research Council)

ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium). It is a specific legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of Research Infrastructures with European interest, as defined in the Council Regulation (EU) No 1261/2013 of 2 December 2013 amending Regulation (EC) No 723/2009.

ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures)

ESG (Environment, Social and Governance)

Facility. A unit within an organization whose staff and/or equipment can be accessed for the purpose of research, e.g., a scientific laboratory, a conservation workshop, a history department.

FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable). Set of guiding principles in order to make data.

FIXLAB (FIXed LABoratory of E-RIHS). E-RIHS access platform that brings together fixed research facilities and associated scientific experience of their staff that develop and maintain sophisticated state-of-the-art instrumentation for advanced diagnostics and archaeometry (<https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/>)

GA (General Assembly). The highest decision-making body of E-RIHS ERIC, comprising representatives from all member (with voting rights), observer and permanent observer countries. It approves strategic plans, budgets, and policies, ensuring alignment with ERIC objectives. The Central Hub acts as the secretariat of this body.

GDP (Gross Domestic Product)

GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation)

GSO (Group of Senior Officials on global research infrastructures)

Host Country. The country hosting the statutory seat of an ERIC, which, in the case of E-RIHS ERIC, is Italy.

Host Fee. The annual financial contribution, provided by the host country, towards the operation of the E-RIHS ERIC.

HS (Heritage Science). The interdisciplinary domain of scientific study of heritage. Heritage science draws on diverse humanities, sciences and engineering disciplines. It focuses on enhancing the understanding, care and sustainable use of heritage so it can enrich people's lives, both today and in the future. Heritage science is an umbrella term encompassing all forms of scientific inquiry into human works and the combined works of nature and humans, of value to people.

HS Academy (Heritage Science Academy). The training and capacity-building program of E-RIHS ERIC, providing interdisciplinary education in heritage science for both users and providers. It features workshops, summer schools, webinars, and specialized training modules for researchers and professionals.

ICT (Information and Communications Technologies)

IPR (Intellectual Property Rights)

ISO (International Organization for Standardization)

KPI (Key Performance Indicator)

MOLAB (MOBile LABoratory). E-RIHS access platform that brings together European laboratories offering state-of-the-art mobile equipment and related competencies, for in-situ non-destructive measurements of artworks, collections, monuments and sites (<https://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-catalogue-of-services/>)

MoU (Memorandum of Understanding)

MS (Member State of the European Union).

MSCA (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions)

NC (National Coordinator). The person responsible of a National Node, designated by the corresponding Member. Within the remit of the NC are representation of national interests, provision of the interface and point of contact between the national level and the E-RIHS ERIC.

NN (National Node). Organization or entity designated by a Member coordinating national E-RIHS resources and organising Member contributions to E-RIHS ERIC. Each National Node has a National Coordinator, appointed by an appropriate authority of the Member. National Nodes should have suitable legal forms to establish Service Level Agreements with the ERIC.

Platform. An integrated set of facilities, resources and services accessible to the E-RIHS users. There are four E-RIHS platforms: ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB.

PRP, Peer Review Panel. The E-RIHS Peer Review Panel evaluates access proposals. It is constituted of world-class experts, both researchers and professionals, and covers a wide range of knowledge and expertise within the field of heritage science.

R&I (Research and Innovation)

RI (Research Infrastructure). “Facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include: major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e-infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation.”, EU Regulation No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013.

SEAB (Scientific and Ethical Advisory Board). An independent external body, composed of distinguished scientists and other experts, appointed by the General Assembly to give advice on scientific and ethical issues arising from the implementation of E-RIHS. The Central Hub acts as the secretariat of this body.

SLA (Service-Level Agreement). Agreement between E-RIHS ERIC and the legal entity operating a National Node regulating the provision of services and resources to support the operation of E-RIHS.

SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities)

STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics)

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